

21NRM02 Digital-IT

D3: Report on existing and new algorithms with their corresponding uncertainty estimation, including a software system for controlling, handling and processing SV data streams for sampling rates up to 96 kSa/s

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1 Summary

This report, part of the 21NRM02 Digital-IT project, presents a comprehensive evaluation of existing and newly developed algorithms for processing Sampled Value (SV) data streams in digital substations, with a focus on high-precision parameter evaluation and uncertainty estimation and at sampling rates up to 96 kSa/s. The study introduces several signal processing techniques including cubic spline, upsample-filter-decimate resampling and windowed RMS. These algorithms are assessed for their ability to estimate amplitude, phase, frequency, power, and harmonic content under asynchronous sampling and noise. A dedicated approach for DC transient decay time estimation is also proposed. Performance comparisons and Monte Carlo uncertainty analyses highlight the trade-offs between accuracy and computational complexity. Finally, the algorithms were integrated into the QWTB framework and accompanied by a graphical user interface to support widespread adoption in metrology and power system diagnostics.

2 Introduction

This report covers the following deliverable description:

Report on existing and new algorithms with corresponding uncertainty estimation, including a software system for controlling, handling, and processing SV data streams for data rates up to 96 kS/s.

To select the relevant parameters that need to be extracted and estimated from a SV data streams, a questionnaire was prepared and sent to the interested parties. A handful of responses were evaluated. The questionnaire is attached as Appendix A. Among other comments, a processing time limitation was considered as important for grid protection, but not for other kind of evaluations. The following parameters to be estimated from the sampled data streams were identified: amplitude, phase, frequency harmonics of the voltage and current, active and apparent power, and DC transients.

While most of the parameters can be evaluated using available algorithms, publicly available algorithms for DC transients are missing. The algorithms used are described in Chapter 3. While no approach is fundamentally new, we have developed the following algorithms as new, including their full validation and performance analysis: Windowed discrete RMS for amplitude, phase and power (see 3.5); Resampling using spline technique (see 3.3); Resampling using upsampling-filtering-decimation approach based on maximum amplitude error (see Chapter 3.4; and DC time decay estimation algorithm based on decayed sine wave peak values (see 3.7. We have also used already established algorithms for asynchronous signal estimation: Phase sensitive frequency estimator (PSFE), specifically for initial signal frequency determination (see 3.2; Multi harmonic Sine Fitting algorithm, used as a reference non-biased estimator (see 3.6.

In Chapter 4, selected algorithms were compared for their performance using a comprehensive comparison, where signal parameters were changed in a pre-determined ranges and deviations from the true parameter value were collected. Additionally, the processing time for each algorithm was recorded to evaluate its processing efficiency.

Further, Chapter 5 and Appendix C covers a Monte-Carlo analysis, which corroborates the findings from the previous chapter.

Finally, Chapter 6 describes the integrated software package with a graphical user interface, installation, data file formats and resulting format. This software enables a rapid and compre-

hensive evaluation and use of all algorithms and signal processing techniques developed within this project.

3 Existing and new algorithms

3.1 Motivation

Modern electrical substations are increasingly adopting digital technologies for improved reliability, flexibility, and interoperability. A key element in this transition is the deployment of *Stand-Alone Merging Units* (SAMUs), which serve as the interface between traditional instrument transformers and the digital domain. SAMUs are responsible for converting analog voltage and current signals into standardized digital messages known as *Sampled Values* (SV), which are transmitted over Ethernet networks in compliance with IEC 61850-9-2 and related standards.

Each SV stream consists of regularly spaced samples of analog waveforms, captured at fixed nominal sampling rates such as 4 kSa/s, 14.4 kSa/s, or 96 kSa/s. These digital streams are used by protection relays, measurement units, and other devices to perform real-time calculations of electrical quantities such as RMS values, power, phase angles, and harmonics.

However, a fundamental challenge arises from the fact that the nominal power system frequency (typically 50 Hz) is not perfectly constant. In practice, it may drift slightly due to changes in generation and load. Since the SV sampling clock is typically not phase-locked to the instantaneous line frequency, the sampling process is inherently *asynchronous* with respect to the signal's actual periodicity. This misalignment causes spectral leakage, reduces the accuracy of frequency-domain analyses, and complicates the estimation of time-domain parameters.

As a result, precise signal processing algorithms are required to extract meaningful electrical quantities from SV data streams. These algorithms must be designed to account for asynchronous sampling, frequency drift, and the presence of noise, while operating within the constraints of real-time performance, computational efficiency, and compliance with relevant accuracy classes.

3.1.1 Accuracy Objectives and Use Cases

The primary goal of this work is to identify and evaluate algorithms capable of extracting voltage, current, phase, active and apparent power, and harmonic content from SV data with very high accuracy. Specifically, we aim for a maximum error within **50 parts per million (ppm)**, corresponding to 0.005%. This stringent margin is motivated by applications requiring Class 0.05 accuracy or better, such as precision metering and advanced diagnostics, and includes a conservative safety factor of $10\times$ to account for cumulative errors in the signal chain.

We consider both:

- **Fast algorithms** intended for real-time or near-real-time applications, where latency and computational load must be minimized.
- **High-accuracy algorithms** used for post-processing, calibration, or benchmarking purposes, where ultimate precision is prioritized over speed.

3.1.2 Overview of Evaluated Methods

To address the challenges outlined above, we investigated a range of signal processing techniques:

Fast and Efficient Methods:

- **Resampling with interpolation or decimation:** By reconstructing a coherently sampled signal at a frequency aligned with the actual fundamental, standard tools such as FFT can be applied with reduced spectral leakage. Both spline-based interpolation and a more classical upsampling–filtering–decimation pipeline were tested.
- **Windowed Discrete RMS:** A straightforward but efficient technique that uses time windows to compute the root-mean-square value of the signal in the time domain, suitable for estimating fundamental amplitude under moderate distortion.
- **Windowed FFT:** By applying a time window (e.g., Hann or Blackman) before computing the FFT, spectral leakage is reduced, improving harmonic estimation even under asynchronous sampling.

High-Accuracy Estimation Methods:

- **Multi-Harmonic Sine Fit:** This method models the signal as a sum of sinusoids with unknown amplitudes, phases, and frequencies. Parameters are estimated through numerical optimization, enabling very accurate determination of fundamental and harmonic components, even under non-coherent conditions.
- **Phase Sensitive Frequency Estimator (PSFE):** A technique used to estimate the fundamental frequency with sub-millihertz resolution. This estimate can then be used to guide resampling or initialization of other estimation procedures.

3.1.3 Special Case: DC Transient Estimation

A separate but related use case is the estimation of **DC transient decay times**, particularly during current transformer saturation or circuit breaker switching. This scenario is addressed in the IEC 61869-13 standard, which defines a test waveform and reference decay characteristics. In real systems, such transients are embedded in noise and sampled asynchronously, making them difficult to characterize accurately.

To address this, we developed and evaluated specialized algorithms capable of robustly estimating exponential decay time constants from SV data, even in the presence of noise and limited time resolution. These methods are particularly useful in instrument transformer testing and advanced diagnostics.

3.1.4 Structure of the Report

In the following sections, each of the considered algorithms is presented in detail. We begin with the fast methods suitable for embedded implementation, followed by the more accurate techniques applicable to high-precision metering and calibration. Each algorithm is described in terms of its:

- Mathematical foundation and operating principles,
- Implementation requirements and performance tradeoffs,
- Performance based on synthetic and real SV test data.

Through this structured evaluation, we aim to provide clear guidance on the suitability of different algorithms for specific SV processing tasks, depending on the required accuracy, available computational resources, and real-time constraints.

3.2 Phase Sensitive Frequency Estimation (PSFE)

The first and foundational algorithm evaluated in this work is the *Phase Sensitive Frequency Estimation* (PSFE) algorithm [1]. This algorithm is designed to accurately estimate the fundamental frequency, amplitude, and phase of a sinusoidal signal component in the presence of harmonics and noise. The estimated frequency is then used as an input to other algorithms, such as multi-harmonic sine fitting or resampling-based approaches, where coherent processing or precise signal alignment is essential.

PSFE is particularly well suited for scenarios involving non-coherent sampling—where the signal’s fundamental period does not align with an integer number of sampling intervals. This condition is typical in Sampled Value (SV) streams, where the system frequency may vary slightly around 50 Hz while the sampling rate remains fixed at 4 kSa/s, 14.4 kSa/s, or 96 kSa/s. Traditional FFT-based methods suffer from spectral leakage under such conditions, leading to degraded frequency resolution and biased amplitude estimation. PSFE overcomes these limitations through a model-based, parametric approach.

3.2.1 Mathematical Foundation

The PSFE method assumes that the measured signal can be represented as the sum of a fundamental sinusoidal component and additional harmonics or noise:

$$x[n] = A_1 \cos(2\pi f_1 n T_s + \phi_1) + d[n],$$

where:

- $x[n]$ is the sampled signal at index n ,
- A_1 , f_1 , and ϕ_1 are the amplitude, frequency, and phase of the fundamental,
- T_s is the sampling interval,
- $d[n]$ is a residual term representing harmonic distortion and additive noise.

The estimation problem involves determining the triplet (A_1, f_1, ϕ_1) from the sampled data. Rather than relying on direct spectral analysis, PSFE uses parametric modeling (Three-parameter sine fit method [2]) and nonlinear optimization to minimize the difference between the measured signal and a synthesized sinusoidal model. Figure 1 shows the PSFE operating principle.

The goodness of the iteration is tested using previous $(j - 1)$ and last (j) iteration estimated phase difference by a cost function

$$\varepsilon = \frac{|\Delta\hat{\phi}_{e,j-1} - \Delta\hat{\phi}_{e,j}|}{2\pi N T_s d\hat{f}_{j-1}}, \quad (1)$$

which will converge toward zero with each new iteration. The process is finished when ε is smaller than a predefined value, in our case 10^{-10} . In practice, this algorithm (PSFE) typically needs only a few iterations to converge to its final value.

Figure 1: Estimation of sampled signal frequency by measuring phase difference between sampled data windows W_1 and W_2 .

What distinguishes PSFE from a more common sine-fitting techniques (i.e. Four parameter sine fit [2]) is its robust suppression of harmonic interference. It achieves this by leveraging the orthogonality properties of sinusoids and fitting the signal in a narrow band around the fundamental frequency. Harmonic components, being at different frequencies, contribute only weakly to the error surface near the true fundamental, allowing the estimator to converge accurately despite the presence of distortion. This is especially effective when additional interpolation is used to cover exactly an integer number of signal cycles [3].

The PSFE method used in this work is based on the detailed formulation presented in [1]. This and other publications have established PSFE as a de facto standard in frequency estimation for metrology applications.

3.2.2 Implementation Considerations

The PSFE algorithm is implemented in the following sequence:

1. **Initial Estimate:** A coarse frequency estimate is obtained using a peak search in the FFT spectrum or by an interpolating DFT routine. This serves to initialize the optimization algorithm.
2. **Nonlinear Optimization:** A local minimization procedure (looking for phase difference between t_w is used to refine the frequency estimate by minimizing the squared error between the measured signal and the sinusoidal model.
3. **Amplitude and Phase Estimation:** Once the optimal frequency is found, a least-squares solution is computed for amplitude and phase, typically by solving an overdetermined linear system using sine and cosine projections.

PSFE is moderately computationally intensive, especially due to the nonlinear optimization step, but remains tractable for real-time or near-real-time processing on modern embedded hardware when operating on short signal windows (requires minimum of two fundamental cycles). The algorithm is also relatively robust to even high levels of additive noise and quantization effects, making it well suited for practical SV data.

3.2.3 Role Within the Processing Chain

In this work, PSFE is not used in isolation, but rather as a core enabler for other algorithms. Specifically:

- In the **multi-harmonic sine fitting** approach, PSFE provides the initial estimate of the fundamental frequency, which improves convergence and reduces risk of local minima during the fitting process.
- In the **resampling-based FFT** methods, PSFE provides a reference frequency used to compute the appropriate resampling ratio, enabling conversion of asynchronously sampled signals into coherently sampled ones.

By providing a highly accurate and robust estimate of the true fundamental frequency, PSFE serves as the starting point for further signal processing and spectral analysis, particularly in metrological applications requiring sub-ppm precision.

3.2.4 Limitations and Assumptions

While PSFE is efficient and bias free, its performance depends on certain signal characteristics:

- The algorithm assumes the signal is dominated by a strong and relatively stable fundamental component.
- Strong non-sinusoidal distortions (e.g., large transients, switching noise) may reduce accuracy unless adequately filtered.
- The sampled signal contains at least two full signal cycles.

Nevertheless, within its intended use case—stationary or slowly time-varying signals with mild to moderate harmonic content—PSFE remains an effective method currently available for frequency estimation from asynchronously sampled data.

3.3 Method 1: Cubic Spline Interpolation

Following the estimation of the fundamental signal frequency using the PSFE algorithm, the next processing step is to convert the asynchronously sampled SV data into a signal that appears to be coherently sampled with respect to its actual periodicity. This transformation allows for accurate frequency-domain analysis using standard FFT techniques, eliminating spectral leakage and aligning the discrete-time window with an integer number of signal periods.

Two complementary resampling strategies were considered:

1. A **cubic spline interpolation** approach, which directly reconstructs the continuous-time waveform and evaluates it on a new, uniformly spaced time grid synchronized to the signal's fundamental period.
2. An **upsampling–filtering–decimation** approach, which approximates ideal bandlimited interpolation using digital filters designed to bound interpolation error (see Sec. 3.4).

Both techniques serve the same purpose: to enable the application of FFT analysis on an effective coherent sampling basis, despite the original asynchronous acquisition.

3.3.1 Overview of the Processing Chain

The complete processing chain consists of the following steps:

1. **Frequency Estimation:** Estimate the fundamental frequency f of the input SV signal using the PSFE algorithm (see Section 3.2).
2. **Timing Vector Construction:** Construct a new timing vector t_k such that:

$$t_k = t_0 + kT', \quad \text{where} \quad T' = \frac{1}{f} \cdot \frac{1}{M}, \quad (2)$$

and $M \in \mathbb{N}$ determines the number of samples per cycle (e.g., $M = 256$).

3. **Signal Resampling:** Interpolate the original discrete-time signal onto the new time vector t_k using one of the two resampling methods described below.

4. **FFT Analysis:** Apply FFT to the resampled signal to compute amplitude, phase, RMS, and harmonic magnitudes at integer harmonics of the estimated fundamental.

The first method models the signal as a continuous-time function by constructing a piecewise cubic polynomial between each pair of known samples. This is a classical technique in numerical analysis and provides third-order accuracy [4].

3.3.2 Mathematical Foundation

Given known samples $(x_0, y_0), \dots, (x_N, y_N)$, the cubic spline interpolant $S(x)$ is defined piecewise over each interval $[x_i, x_{i+1}]$ as:

$$S_i(x) = a_i + b_i(x - x_i) + c_i(x - x_i)^2 + d_i(x - x_i)^3. \quad (3)$$

The coefficients are determined to satisfy:

- Interpolation at knots: $S_i(x_i) = y_i, \quad S_i(x_{i+1}) = y_{i+1}$,
- Smoothness: $S(x), S'(x), S''(x)$ continuous over entire domain,
- Boundary conditions: usually natural ($S''(x_0) = S''(x_N) = 0$) or clamped ($S'(x_0), S'(x_N)$ specified).

To compute the spline, a tridiagonal system is solved for the second derivatives $M_i = S''(x_i)$, leading to the following compact spline formula over $[x_i, x_{i+1}]$:

$$S_i(x) = \frac{M_{i+1}(x - x_i)^3}{6h_i} + \frac{M_i(x_{i+1} - x)^3}{6h_i} + \left(\frac{y_{i+1}}{h_i} - \frac{M_{i+1}h_i}{6} \right) (x - x_i) + \left(\frac{y_i}{h_i} - \frac{M_i h_i}{6} \right) (x_{i+1} - x), \quad (4)$$

where $h_i = x_{i+1} - x_i$.

Cubic spline interpolation is then used to evaluate:

$$x_{\text{resampled}}[k] = S(t_k). \quad (5)$$

This yields a signal sampled coherently with respect to the actual waveform, enabling clean FFT-based extraction of amplitude, phase, and harmonic content.

Cubic spline interpolation is computationally efficient and well-suited for smooth signals, but care must be taken in presence of high noise or sharp transitions, where overfitting or overshoot may occur.

3.3.3 Advantages:

- Simple to implement and provides smooth interpolation.
- No aliasing introduced, since no upsampling is involved.
- High accuracy for bandlimited signals with relatively smooth content.

3.3.4 Limitations:

- Sensitive to noise and high-frequency content, which can introduce overshoot or ringing in the spline fit.
- Accuracy depends on the sample density relative to the highest signal frequency (Nyquist margin). However, this is not a concern using a high enough sample rate.

3.3.5 FFT-Based Parameter Extraction

Once either resampling method is applied, the resulting signal $x_{\text{coh}}[k]$ is effectively a uniformly sampled sequence over an integer number of cycles. An FFT of this signal provides the harmonic spectrum with minimal leakage. Parameters of interest are then extracted as follows:

- **Fundamental Amplitude and Phase:** Read magnitude and angle at the fundamental frequency FFT bin.
- **RMS Value:** Compute RMS from amplitude or sum of squared bin magnitudes.
- **Harmonics:** Extract amplitudes and phases from integer multiples of the fundamental FFT bin.
- **Power Quantities:** Combine amplitude and phase of voltage and current to compute active and apparent power.

3.4 Method 2: Upsample–Filter–Decimate (UFD) Resampling Method

In applications involving Sampled Values (SV) within the IEC 61850 framework, resampling is often necessary for two key reasons:

1. **Lack of coherent sampling:** The power line frequency f_{line} deviates slightly from its nominal value (e.g., 50 Hz), while the sampling frequency f_s remains fixed. This leads to a non-integer number of samples per period (SPP), causing spectral leakage when applying the DFT.
2. **Need to reduce data rate:** For instance, signals originally sampled at 96 kSa/s may need to be downsampled for processing in IEDs, which prefer an integer power-of-2 SPP (e.g., 256). Resampling allows efficient data rate reduction without degrading spectral integrity.

The Upsample–Filter–Decimate (UFD) method is a flexible and accurate approach to meet these objectives.

3.4.1 Overview of the UFD Procedure

Resampling is performed by a three-stage process:

1. **Upsampling:** Insert $N - 1$ zeros between each sample of the original sequence.
2. **Filtering:** Apply a low-pass FIR filter (the *resample filter*) to interpolate intermediate values and limit bandwidth.

3. **Decimation:** Take every M -th output sample to form the resampled signal at the new rate $(N/M)f_s$.

The interpolation and decimation factors N and M are chosen to meet target resampling conditions, either to achieve a nominal SPP (e.g., 256) or to control spectral leakage error.

3.4.2 Selection of Resampling Factors N and M

Selection of resampling factors M and N is based on maximum allowable leakage error in estimated fundamental tone amplitude using FFT (see App. B, which is defined by maximum error of the number of samples per period δSPP).

3.4.3 Filter Design Considerations

The resample filter is an FIR low-pass filter with the following specifications:

- **Passband edge:** up to the maximum signal frequency (e.g., 2.2 kHz).
- **Stopband start:** $f_{\text{stop}} = \frac{N}{2M}f_s$ to prevent aliasing.
- **Ripple and attenuation:** To ensure 50 ppm amplitude accuracy, the passband ripple must be less than 0.0001%; stopband attenuation was set below -120 dB (see Fig).

The filter can be designed using windowed methods (e.g., Kaiser) in tools like MATLAB or GNU Octave. For example, with:

$$f_s = 12800 \text{ Hz}, N = 5000, M_{\text{max}} = 5102,$$

a FIR filter with 122664 taps was generated to satisfy the criteria. Fig. plots actual filter characteristics used in all simulations reported here.

3.4.4 Computational Considerations

Even though the FIR filter length L may be large, the actual computation per output sample is reduced because only one out of every M samples is retained. For example, the number of multiply-accumulate operations per SPP is:

$$\text{MACs} = \frac{L}{N} \cdot \text{SPP}_{\text{nom}}.$$

For the example above, this yields approximately 6400 MACs for 256 resampled samples.

3.4.5 Noise and Robustness

The UFD method effectively acts as a low-pass filter and provides good noise suppression by design. The use of FIR filters ensures numerical robustness and stability, and the bandwidth can be narrowed further to reduce the influence of high-frequency noise.

Figure 2: Resample low-pass filter characteristic for varying number of taps L and corresponding bandwidths (BW) and stop frequency of 6.4 kHz

3.4.6 Design Flow Summary

The design steps for UFD resampling are:

1. Choose N and compute M from estimated f_{line} .
2. Design the FIR resample filter for worst-case M (typically at $f_{\text{line}} = 49$ Hz).
3. Apply upsampling, filtering, and decimation to the input SV data.
4. Pass the resampled output to an FFT engine for further analysis.

3.4.7 Reference Implementation

Filter design can be implemented using:

- GNU Octave: `fir1()`, `kaiserord()`
- MATLAB: `firpm()`, `firls()`, or `designfilt()`

3.4.8 Summary

Both resampling approaches (Spline resampling and UFD resampling) offer a practical and accurate route to converting asynchronous SV data into a form suitable for FFT-based analysis. Their successful application hinges on an accurate frequency estimate (e.g., from PSFE) and careful resampling design. The choice between spline and filter-based interpolation depends on the desired tradeoff between computational cost, robustness to noise, and ease of implementation.

Performance evaluations of both methods under synthetic and real SV conditions are presented in a later section.

3.5 Windowed RMS Estimation Method

A simple yet effective method for estimating signal parameters from asynchronously sampled data is the use of *windowed RMS* (wRMS) calculations. This method provides computationally lightweight estimates of signal amplitude, active power, and apparent power, and can also be extended to phase estimation between two channels via cross-correlation.

Unlike FFT-based approaches, windowed RMS does not require coherent sampling or re-sampling, making it well-suited for real-time applications and embedded systems. Although less accurate than sine-fitting techniques or resampled FFT under ideal conditions, the wRMS method offers excellent trade-offs when processing noisy or harmonically distorted signals over short time windows.

3.5.1 Signal Model

Consider a sinusoidal signal contaminated by noise and harmonics:

$$x[n] = A \cos(2\pi f n T_s + \phi) + \sum_{k=2}^K A_k \cos(2\pi k f n T_s + \phi_k) + \eta[n],$$

where:

- A , f , and ϕ are the amplitude, frequency, and phase of the fundamental,
- A_k , ϕ_k are amplitudes and phases of harmonic components,
- $\eta[n]$ is zero-mean additive noise.

A rectangular or Hann window of length N is applied to the signal to limit the analysis to a finite interval:

$$w[n] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{rectangular window,} \\ 0.5 \left(1 - \cos \left(\frac{2\pi n}{N-1} \right) \right), & \text{Hann window.} \end{cases}$$

3.5.2 Amplitude and Power Estimation

The windowed RMS value is then calculated on the $V_w(n)$

$$\hat{V}_{\text{wRMS}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{S_2} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} V_w(n)^2}, \quad (6)$$

normalizing the reduced amplitude due to the window function using a sum of squared window values S_2

$$S_2 = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (w(n))^2. \quad (7)$$

Windowed discrete active power is given by

$$\hat{P}_w = \frac{1}{S_2} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} P_w(n). \quad (8)$$

Likewise, windowed discrete apparent power can be obtained from the windowed discrete RMS values for voltage and current

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{S}_w &= V_{w\text{RMS}} \cdot I_{w\text{RMS}} \\ &= \frac{1}{S_2} \sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (V(n)w(n))^2 \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (I(n)w(n))^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

This RMS value reflects the total energy within the window, including the contributions from the fundamental, harmonics, and noise.

3.5.3 Phase Estimation via Cross-Correlation

Signal phase can be determined from

$$\phi = \arccos\left(\frac{V_{\text{RMS}}I_{\text{RMS}}}{P}\right), \quad (10)$$

and

$$\hat{\phi}_w = \arccos\left(\frac{\hat{S}_w}{\hat{P}_w}\right). \quad (11)$$

A cross-correlation is used to determine the positive or negative sign of the calculated phase.

This method is robust in the presence of distortion, though accuracy diminishes particularly with harmonics and less so with noise.

3.5.4 Discussion and Applicability

The wRMS method provides fast, low-latency estimation suitable for:

- Low-cost or resource-constrained platforms,
- Sliding-window signal monitoring,
- Scenarios where frequency varies slowly and coherence cannot be guaranteed.

The primary limitations stem from:

- Sensitivity to harmonics, which inflate the RMS estimate,
- Noise bias, which increases estimation variance,
- Window effects, which trade spectral resolution for temporal responsiveness.

Figure 3 shows the RMS amplitude bias as a function of signal periods and window type.

Figure 3: Relative bias of RMS estimation for different window types in presence of 10 % second and third harmonic.

3.5.5 Conclusion

The windowed RMS method offers a lightweight and practical approach for amplitude, power, and phase estimation from SV data. While not as accurate as parametric methods or FFT on coherently sampled data, it remains useful in real-time environments and provides acceptable performance when harmonic levels are moderate.

Further evaluation under synthetic and real-world SV datasets is provided in the later section. This method is described in detail in [5].

3.6 Multi-Harmonic Sine-Fitting Algorithm

To estimate not only the fundamental component but also multiple harmonics simultaneously, we adopt the multi-harmonic sine-fitting method described by Schoukens, Pintelon, and Vandersteen in IEEE-TIM 1997 [6]. This parametric, least-squares-based technique accurately fits a sum of sinusoids to asynchronously sampled data, accounting for both amplitude and possible time-base distortions or jitter.

3.6.1 Signal Model

The measured signal $x[n]$ over N samples is modeled as:

$$x[n] = \sum_{k=1}^K A_k \cos(2\pi k f n T_s + \phi_k) + d[n],$$

where:

- f is the fundamental frequency (initially obtained via PSFE),

- A_k, ϕ_k are amplitudes and phases of the k -th harmonic (up to K),
- $d[n]$ represents residual error or noise,
- T_s is the original sampling interval.

This extends the simpler single-tone model to capture harmonic distortion explicitly.

3.6.2 Least Squares Formulation

The objective is to minimize the weighted mean-square error:

$$J(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \left(x[n] - \sum_{k=1}^K (a_k \cos(\omega_k n) + b_k \sin(\omega_k n)) \right)^2,$$

where:

$$\omega_k = 2\pi k f T_s, \quad a_k = A_k \cos \phi_k, \quad b_k = -A_k \sin \phi_k.$$

This regression is linear in the parameters $\{a_k, b_k\}$ when f is held fixed. A second-level optimization adjusts the fundamental f to minimize the residual error. This nonlinear iterative minimization is initialized with f from PSFE, ensuring robust convergence.

3.6.3 Amplitude, Phase, and Harmonic Extraction

Once \hat{f} and $\hat{\mathbf{p}}$ are found, parameters are recovered as:

$$A_k = \sqrt{a_k^2 + b_k^2}, \quad \phi_k = \arctan 2(-b_k, a_k).$$

From these, RMS values, active/apparent power, and harmonic distortion metrics are computed using standard formulas.

3.6.4 Advantages and Practical Considerations

Key strengths:

- Accurate separation of fundamental and harmonic components even under asynchronous sampling, without introducing any processing bias, as long as all signal components are accounted for. In case they are not, generated bias is bound as for Four Parameter Sine Fit Algorithm [7].
- Superior leakage suppression compared to windowed FFT.
- Flexibility in modeling multiple harmonics/interharmonics simultaneously.

Practical constraints:

- Matrix inversion becomes computationally heavier with increasing K .
- All relevant signal component frequency ratios to the fundamental shall be known in advance.

3.6.5 Implementation Notes

Our implementation adopts the following approach:

1. Estimate f via PSFE.
2. Build $\mathbf{H}(f)$ for desired K (typically up to the 10th harmonic).
3. Solve normal equations using efficient linear algebra routines.
4. Refine f by re-minimizing residual error over a narrow band around the initial PSFE estimate.

3.6.6 Role in the Processing Chain

The multi-harmonic fitting method is the most comprehensive of the algorithms evaluated. It provides high-accuracy estimates for amplitude, phase, harmonics, and derived quantities directly, without requiring resampling or FFT—though at a higher computational cost. It is used for benchmarking, metrology-grade analysis, and embedded reference implementations where computational load permits.

3.7 DC Decay time parameter algorithm

During some faults in power system, like for instance a short circuit across generator terminals, a decaying DC component may be present in a measured current signal. Standard IEC 61869-13 defines a decay time as a main parameter to be measured and determined in such occasions.

3.7.1 Problem definition

Fig. 4 shows the decay time definition from the expected DC offset induced in the line frequency signal.

Time domain analysis is required to measure the time constant T_1 of the DC component of the rated short-circuit current I_{SC} on which the transient performance of the device is based on (see IEC 61869-13 Instrument Transformers – Part 13: Stand-alone Merging Unit (SAMU), chapter 3.4.1301).

Figure 4: DC decay definition as per IEC 61869-13 standard.

3.7.2 Proposed decay time algorithms

We have investigated three approaches, first with fitting a decayed sinusoid to the data, second using peak sine values to determine the decay function and third being a combination of the two (see App. D).

While all three approaches provide a good estimate under a relatively clean signal situations (e.g. low noise), the peak value based method provided better results, with the capability to improve it further by taking into account both positive and negative peak values.

3.7.3 Conclusions

Three approaches (peak-detect approach, fitting approach and combined approach) have been tested for estimation of DC decay parameters. The general conclusions are:

Accuracy performance:

- Fitting approach can provide very accurate results with zero error. However, on average the peak-detect based approach is more accurate. Moreover, the maximal error obtained by peak-detect approach are much smaller compared to fitting approach. The combined approach showed the best overall accuracy performance even under quite severe presence of noise.
- The peak-detect approach is not suitable for low B value ($B = 6 \text{ 1/s}$ and $B = 10 \text{ 1/s}$). The combined approach does not have an issue with that because fitting function can resolve inaccurate initial guess of B.
- The peak-detect approach is not suitable for high RMS Noise (1 V).
- Peak-detect approach (and combined approach) requires detection of at least three peaks.

Requirements:

- Peak-detect approach is always significantly faster than fitting approach. The combined approach requires about twice as much computational time as peak-detect approach (half of that time is needed for peak-detect analysis, but after good estimates are obtained also the fitting function finds the solution relatively fast).
- The peak-detect approach requires only a low-level Matlab function (free, works in Octave) while the fitting and combined approach algorithm require Curve Fitting Toolbox (extra cost in addition to Matlab licence).

4 Comparison of algorithms (except for DC Decay)

The performance of algorithms can be easily compared using simulation of signals, application of algorithms and comparing the results. The advantage is the parameters of the simulated signals are known thus the error of the algorithms can be evaluated correctly. To get useful results, simulated signals must be generated with parameters similar to the intended use-case. The simulation procedure was following:

- Select values of signal parameters,
- generate a waveform based on the parameters,
- apply algorithms to the generated waveform,
- calculate error of signal parameters estimation.

4.1 Compared algorithms

Following algorithms were compared and are marked as following:

- WDFT – windowed discrete Fourier transformation, the selected flattop window 248D [8] is optimised for the lowest sidelobe level achievable with 10 cosine terms and value of normalized equivalent noise bandwidth is 5.6512 bins. Algorithm calculates whole spectrum.
- PSFE – the algorithm was optimized to estimate frequency, described in Algorithm calculates only amplitude and phase of the fundamental component.
- MHFE – Multi-Harmonic Frequency Estimation, the algorithm is described in Algorithm calculates amplitude and phase of the fundamental component and harmonic components. Which harmonic components are estimated is an input to the algorithm.
- Spline Resampling – the algorithm is described in chapter 3.3 Algorithm calculates whole spectrum.
- resampling SV stream – the algorithm is described in chapter 3.4. Algorithm calculates whole spectrum.
- Windowed RMS – the algorithm is described in chapter Algorithm calculates only root mean square (RMS) value of the signal.

Because algorithms calculates different parameters, the results show only relevant algorithms. E.g. errors of 2nd harmonic component is not shown for Windowed RMS and PSFE.

4.1.1 Example of a spectrum

For better understanding of the algorithms, figure 5 shows an example of a signal spectrum calculated by Fourier transformation with a rectangular window, WDFT, Spline Resampling and resampling SV stream algorithms. The sampling was deliberately set to non-coherent thus one can observe noise levels and spectral leakage.

Figure 5: Example of a signal spectrum calculated by Fourier transformation with a rectangular window, WDFT, Spline Resampling and resampling SV stream algorithms. Signal was non-coherently sampled and contains also 5th harmonic component. The signal and sampling properties were selected to generate evident figure.

4.1.2 Default values

The parameters of the simulated signals were selected to match the intended use in the SAMU:

- The frequency of the main signal component was selected as 50 Hz, and was varied from 49.5 Hz to 50.5 Hz.
- The amplitude of the main component in SAMU devices is dependent on the applied signal, transducers, and full scale range of internal analogue-to-digital converters. Because this document does not simulate a real hardware but focus on data processing, amplitude of value 1 V was selected for simulated waveforms.
- The phase of the main signal component was selected as 0 rad and varied from $-\pi$ to π .
- The noise in the signal was simulated as Gaussian noise with base value of 0 V and varied up to 1 mV.
- The sampling frequency was set to 96 kHz and varied down to 4.8 kHz.
- The length of the sampled data stream was set to 5 signal periods and varied up to 100.
- Additionally, several simulations were repeated with added third harmonic component of amplitude 0.1 V.

4.2 Comparison results

The following influences were considered:

- signal frequency, see chapter 4.3,
- sampling frequency, see chapter 4.4,
- number of periods in the record,
- influence of third harmonic,
- noise level.

4.3 Influence of the signal frequency

Results are shown in figures 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16.

The signal frequency was varied in the range from 49.9 Hz to 50.1 Hz. All considered algorithms showed out amplitude errors smaller than 7×10^{-8} V. The WDFT windowed properties resulted in 'U' shape of the error. The errors of SplineResample, always smaller than 6×10^{-13} V, follow up errors of the PSFE algorithm. This behaviour is understandable because SplineResample use PSFE to estimate the resampling coefficients. MHFE errors were at the level of numerical precision 1×10^{-16} V. The phase errors varies from -40 mrad to 40 mrad for WDFT and less than 2×10^{-8} mrad for other algorithms.

The calculation time of the resampling algorithm is the highest, followed by SplineResample, PSFE, windowed FFT, windowed RMS and MHFE being the fastest one.

For the case of added 2nd, 3rd, and 5thharmonic signal of amplitude one-tenth of the main signal, the results changes substantially. Especially the spectral leakage of the 2ndharmonic cause large amplitude errors of the fundamental component when estimated by the windowed FFT algorithm. This is not the case for SplineResample, errors are kept below $0.1 \mu\text{V}$. However phase estimation is not affected.

Only SplineResample and WDFT algorithms (from the selected ones) can also estimate properties of the simulated 2nd, 3rdand 5thharmonic components. The amplitude errors of the SplineResample algorithm are below $0.2 \mu\text{V}$, and errors of the MHFE are below 1×10^{-11} V.

Figure 6: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the signal frequency. Signal without harmonic content.

Figure 7: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the signal frequency. Signal without harmonic content. A constant phase error reflects a time delay, that can be compensated numerically.

Figure 8: Dependence of algorithm calculation time on the signal frequency. Signal without harmonic content.

Figure 9: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the signal frequency. Signal with added 2nd harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of main component amplitude.

Figure 10: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the signal frequency. Signal with added 2ndharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of main component amplitude.

Figure 11: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the signal frequency. Signal with added 2ndharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 2nd component amplitude.

Figure 12: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the signal frequency. Signal with added 2ndharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 2ndcomponent amplitude.

Figure 13: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the signal frequency. Signal with added 3rdharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 3rdcomponent amplitude.

Figure 14: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the signal frequency. Signal with added 3rdharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 3rdcomponent amplitude.

Figure 15: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the signal frequency. Signal with added 5thharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 5thcomponent amplitude.

Figure 16: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the signal frequency. Signal with added 5th harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 5th component amplitude.

4.4 Influence of the sampling frequency

Results are shown in figures 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25. The sampling frequency was varied in the range from 4 kHz to 96 kHz.

The errors of both amplitude and phase are decreasing for increasing sampling frequency for all algorithms but the resampling algorithm, that keeps the error just below specified maximum error. However the fastest decrease is for the SplineResample and MHFE algorithms.

Figure 17: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the sampling frequency. Signal without harmonic content.

Figure 18: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the sampling frequency. Signal without harmonic content.

Figure 19: Dependence of algorithm calculation time on the sampling frequency. Signal without harmonic content.

Figure 20: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the sampling frequency. Signal with added 2nd harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 2nd component amplitude.

Figure 21: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the sampling frequency. Signal with added 2nd harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 2nd component amplitude.

Figure 22: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the sampling frequency. Signal with added 3rd harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 3rd component amplitude.

Figure 23: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the sampling frequency. Signal with added 3rd harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 3rd component amplitude.

Figure 24: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the sampling frequency. Signal with added 5th harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 5th component amplitude.

Figure 25: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the sampling frequency. Signal with added 5th harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 5th component amplitude.

4.5 Influence of the record length

Results are shown in figures 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34. The length of the sampled record was varied in the range from 2 main signal periods to 20 signal periods.

Figure 26: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the record length. Signal without harmonic content.

Figure 27: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the record length. Signal without harmonic content.

Figure 28: Dependence of algorithm calculation time on the record length. Signal without harmonic content.

Figure 29: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the record length. Signal with added 2ndharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 2ndcomponent amplitude.

Figure 30: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the record length. Signal with added 2ndharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 2ndcomponent amplitude.

Figure 31: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the record length. Signal with added 3rdharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 3rdcomponent amplitude.

Figure 32: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the record length. Signal with added 3rdharmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 3rdcomponent amplitude.

Figure 33: Dependence of algorithm amplitude errors on the record length. Signal with added 5th harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 5th component amplitude.

Figure 34: Dependence of algorithm phase errors on the record length. Signal with added 5th harmonic component. Errors are shown for estimation of the 5th component amplitude.

4.6 Influence of the maximum allowed error of the resampling algorithm

The most important input parameter of the resampling algorithm is the maximum allowed error. The figures 35 and 36 show the influence of this parameter on the amplitude and phase errors of the main component.

For all settings of the parameter, the algorithm kept errors below the specified value.

Figure 35: Dependence of the resampling algorithm amplitude error on the input parameter maximum allowed error.

Figure 36: Dependence of the resampling algorithm phase error on the input parameter maximum allowed error.

4.7 Conclusion on the algorithm comparison

The MHFE algorithm outperforms all other algorithms by orders. However the number and orders of the considered harmonic components has to be precisely known in advance, thus this algorithm is not at all suitable for estimation of unknown or spectrally polluted signal.

The SplineResample algorithm delivers the second best results, and the errors of this algorithm are very correlated to the error of the signal frequency estimate. Thus the errors in the figures are very similar to the errors of the PSFE algorithm, that was used to make the estimate. The advantage is this algorithm delivers full spectrum, the disadvantage is the time of the calculation.

The windowed RMS algorithm is very fast, delivers small errors, but only calculates RMS values.

The resampling algorithm is the slowest to calculate, yet it is the only algorithm for which the maximum amplitude error of the fundamental component can be set in advance. This algorithm is not useful for the estimation of the phase.

4.8 Proposal of the processing of an unknown signal

Based on the results, the best approach to process an unknown signal is following:

- If only RMS value is needed:
 1. use Windowed RMS algorithm.
- If full spectrum is needed:
 1. Estimate the frequency of the fundamental component using PSFE algorithm.
 2. Resample the signal using SplineResample algorithm, and use the result of PSFE as an input.
 3. Obtain full spectrum of the resampled signal using FFT algorithm (no window).
 4. If number of harmonics is reasonably small, use MHFE algorithm to estimate amplitudes and phases of the harmonic components to achieve even smaller errors than by using SplineResample algorithm.

4.9 How to run simulations

- install, setup QWTB
- add algorithms from *algorithms_for_QWTB/* in repository [9] to QWTB directory,
- run *resampling_test_all.m* in GNU Octave or MATLAB.

When using MS Windows operating system, one will likely need to change paths in *resampling_test_all.m* to use Windows backslashes instead of normal slashes in file paths.

4.10 Notes on replotting the figures

To replot the presented figures, following has to be done. First, in Octave/Matlab one has to change to the directory with saved results. Now one has to either directly open figure in GNU Octave using the following code:

```

1 h = openfig('varied_M_h1_AErr_hm_1.fig');
2 set(h, 'visible', 'on');
```

or fully replot the data:

- load file with output data, e.g. *varied_M_h1/varied_M_h1input_and_plot_data.mat*,
- replot using function *make_plot* according the lines 129-135 in file *resampling_test.m*:

```

1     make_plot('AErr', 'Amplitude error', ndres, ndaxes,
2             harm_multiple, 1, file_prefix, xlabel, alg_prefixes
3             );
4     make_plot('phErr', 'Phase error', ndres, ndaxes,
5             harm_multiple, 1, file_prefix, xlabel, alg_prefixes
6             );
7     make_plot('ct', 'Calculation time', ndres, ndaxes,
8             harm_multiple, 1, file_prefix, xlabel, alg_prefixes
9             );
10    if harm_multiple > 1
11        make_plot('AErr', 'Amplitude error', ndres, ndaxes,
12                harm_multiple, 2, file_prefix, xlabel,
13                alg_prefixes);
14        make_plot('phErr', 'Phase error', ndres, ndaxes,
15                harm_multiple, 2, file_prefix, xlabel,
16                alg_prefixes);
17    end
```

5 Algorithm performance and uncertainty evaluation

The uncertainty analysis of the algorithms was performed using several Monte-Carlo simulations in MATLAB software. The first important step is to generate the voltage and the current waveforms that are inputs for the algorithms. In our case we generated the voltage waveform using Eq. 1 and current waveform using Eq. 2. In principle both equations consist of fundamental voltage and the current, four additional harmonics that also need to be estimated by the algorithms. Additionally, both waveforms contain a few additional harmonic components having smaller amplitudes that act as disturbance for the algorithm. These spurious harmonics were randomly selected between 6th and 50th harmonic and the number of those spurious harmonics has been defined by the N_{harm} parameter (between 0 and 5). In addition to spurious harmonics, also a random noise has been added to the voltage and current waveform. The shape of the noise waveform for every simulation was always random. However, for noise waveforms we controlled the RMS value, and we checked that the DC value of the noise was practically zero.

$$U(t) = \sum_{k=1}^5 U_k \cdot \sin(2\pi kft + \varphi_{k,U}) + U_{\text{noise}} \cdot \text{rnd}(t) \quad (12)$$

$$I(t) = \sum_{k=1}^5 I_k \cdot \sin(2\pi kft + \varphi_{k,I}) + I_{\text{noise}} \cdot \text{rnd}(t) \quad (13)$$

The simulator also considers the jitter effect, Eq. 3. In this case a small random deviation of the time has been added to the idea time vector. Again, the overall RMS value of the jitter can be controlled by jitterRMS parameter, the DC value of the time deviation is zero again, but otherwise, the variation is random. This time vector with jitter effect has been included for all parts of the waveform, i.e., fundamental signal, harmonics, spurious harmonics and noise. However, for each simulation the same time vector has been used for voltage and current waveform generation (i.e., we assume that the effect of jitter is the same when sampling voltage or current waveforms since sampling is performed at the same time).

$$t = t_s + t_{\text{jitter}} \cdot \text{rnd}(t) \quad (14)$$

It is evident that Eqs. 1-3 contains multiple parameters that can be generally divided into two groups. In the first group are parameters that are systematically varied and strictly tracked. Usually, they are the parameters that needs to be estimated by the algorithms. In the second group are the parameters that are randomly varied. Those parameters are changed for every Monte-Carlo simulation. On contrary, the systematically varied parameters are generally varied much less often and only when we want to change the parameter in a sensitivity analysis or when we want to perform another sensitivity analysis (more details are given below).

A detailed Monte Carlo analysis is given in App. C, where all systematically varied parameters are given with all results tabularly collected.

6 Integrated software package

The goal of the integrated software package is to simplify adoption of the algorithms by other parties, and to provide a simple Graphical User Interface (GUI) for the algorithms.

The developed algorithms were integrated into QWTB [10], and an GUI optimized for the processing of the SAMMU data was developed.

6.1 Integration of the algorithms into the QWTB

Algorithms integrated into QWTB are available in directory *algorithms_for_QWTB/* of the repository [9]. How to use algorithms in the QWTB framework is described in the QWTB documentation [10].

6.1.1 Algorithm *resamplingSVstream*

The algorithm input and output quantities follows:

- Input quantities:
 - Sampling period T_s (s) or sampling frequency f_s (Hz) or time series t (s).
 - Sampled values y (V).
 - Estimate of fundamental component frequency f_{est} (Hz).
 - Maximum relative error of the signal amplitude $max_rel_A_err$ (optional) (V/V).
 - Anti-aliasing filter coefficients AA_filter (optional).
 - Stop frequency of the anti-aliasing filter AA_stop (optional) (Hz). Value is overridden if AA_filter is used.
 - Relative passband ripple of the anti-aliasing filter AA_ripple (optional) (V/V). Value is overridden if AA_filter is used.
 - Attenuation of the anti-aliasing filter AA_att (optional) (dB). Value is overridden if AA_filter is used.
 - Required number of samples per period of the signal SPP .
 - Anti-aliasing FIR filter coefficients AA_filter . Overrides inputs AA_stop , AA_ripple , AA_att .
- Output quantities:
 - Sampling frequency after resampling f_s (Hz).
 - Sampling period after resampling T_s (s).
 - Time series after resampling t (s).
 - Resampled samples y (V).
 - Multiplication coefficient used for resampling N .
 - Decimation coefficient used for resampling M .
 - Coefficients of the used anti-aliasing FIR filter AA_filter .

6.1.2 Example of resamplingSVstream usage

```

1 fs = 12800;
2 L = 2*1280;
3 t = [0:L-1] ./ fs;
4 f = 49.25;
5 DISampled.y.v = sin(2.*pi.*f.*t + 0);
6 DISampled.fs.v = fs;
7 DISampled.fest.v = f;
8
9 %% Signal frequency estimate:
10 Estimate = qwtb('PSFE', DISampled);
11 DISampled.fest.v = Estimate.f.v;
12
13 %% Call algorithm:
14 CS.verbose = 1;
15 DOResampled = qwtb('resamplingSVstream', DISampled, CS);
16
17 %% Get spectra:
18 SpectrumResampled = qwtb('SP-WFFT', DOResampled);

```

6.1.3 Algorithm *SplineResample*

- Input quantities:
 - Sampling period T_s (s) or sampling frequency f_s (Hz) or time series t (s).
 - Sampled values y (V).
 - Estimate of fundamental component frequency f_{est} (Hz).
 - Method of resampling: 'keepN', 'minimizefs', 'poweroftwo' (optional).
 - Denominator to reduce resampled bandwidth D (optional).
- Output quantities:
 - Sampling frequency after resampling f_s (Hz).
 - Sampling period after resampling T_s (s).
 - Time series after resampling t (s).
 - Resampled samples y (V).
 - Integer upsampling factor Pf .
 - Integer decimation factor Qf .
 - Method of resampling *method*.

6.1.4 Example of SplineResample usage

```

1 f = 49.77;
2 N = 2000;
3 fs = 4000;
4 Ts = 1/fs;
5 Sampled.t.v = [0 : N-1] * Ts;
6 Sampled.y.v = sin(2 * pi * f * Sampled.t.v);
7
8 %% Signal frequency estimate:
9 Estimate = qwtb('PSFE', Sampled);
10 Sampled.fest.v = Estimate.f.v;
11
12 %% Call algorithm:
13 Resampled = qwtb('SplineResample', Sampled);
14
15 %% Get spectra:
16 SpectrumResampled = qwtb('SP-WFFT', Resampled);

```

6.1.5 Algorithm *windowedRMS*

- Input quantities:
 - Sampled values y (V).
 - Sampled voltage u (V).
 - Sampled current i (A) (optional).
 - Name of window function $window$ (optional).
- Output quantities:
 - RMS amplitude of a single signal A (V or A).
 - RMS amplitude of a voltage signal U (V).
 - RMS amplitude of a current signal I (A).
 - Windowed active power P (W).
 - Windowed apparent power S (VA).
 - Effective phase shift phi_{ef} (rad).
 - Power factor PF .

6.1.6 Example of *windowedRMS* usage

```

1 t = (0 : 1000-1) * 1/4000;
2 DI.y.v = sin(2*pi * 50 * t);
3
4 %% Calculate RMS:
5 D0 = qwtb('windowedRMS', DI);

```

6.2 Description of the Graphical User Interface

The script `proc_SAMMU_waveform_gui` is used to generate Graphical User Interface (GUI), and to calculate signal properties using algorithms developed under the scope of the project. Sampled data can be loaded from `.pcap` or `.csv` files.

6.3 Requirements of the Graphical User Interface

User needs either GNU Octave [11] or Matlab [12].

Optionally, Wireshark [13] and its console version `tshark` (included in standard installation) are needed to read and convert `.pcap` or `.pcapng` files.

User may also need the Q-Wave Toolbox [10] and algorithms from the EPMDigitalITsw repository [9], but these are automatically downloaded during the first run.

If user use MSYS2 (on Windows), user will need `unzip` for auto-installation of QWTB and Digital-IT algorithms.

6.4 How to Install and Run GUI

1. Download the script `proc_SAMMU_waveform_gui.m` [14] using “Download raw file”.
2. Run GNU Octave or Matlab and start the script using:

```
proc_SAMMU_waveform_gui
```

6.4.1 Manual Installation

1. Download the script as above.
2. Download QWTB [10] and add it to your Matlab/Octave path.
3. Download Digital-IT algorithms [15] and add to QWTB.
4. Download and install Wireshark [13].

6.5 How to Use GUI

6.5.1 3.1 Main Window

See figure 37.

- `Convert pcap file to csv...`: opens conversion window.
- `Select datafile..`: opens dialog to select input file.
- `Algorithm::` select processing algorithm.
- `Split by (s)`: split data by time in seconds; set 0 to disable.
- `Sampling f (Hz)`: input sampling frequency.
- `Signal frequency (Hz)`: input estimated signal frequency (within 10%).

Figure 37: Main window of the GUI.

- Method, Denominator, etc.: additional algorithm settings.
- Calculate: runs the processing.
- Help: opens this help.

6.5.2 Conversion Window

See figure 38.

Figure 38: Conversion window of the GUI.

- Select pcap datafile...: choose a .pcap or .pcapng file.
- Read MAC addresses: uses tshark to extract addresses.
- Source MAC address, Destination MAC address: select endpoints.
- Convert: runs conversion with tshark.
- Help: opens this help.

6.6 Input Data File Formats for the GUI

- .csv with waveform vectors
- .csv exported from Wireshark [13]
- .mat file with variable `y`
- .pcap or .pcapng

6.6.1 CSV with Waveform Vectors

Each column = one waveform:

```
w1s1, w2s1, ..., wMs1
w1s2, w2s2, ..., wMs2
...
w1sN, w2sN, ..., wMsN
```

6.6.2 CSV from Wireshark

Export using:

File -> Export Packet Dissections -> As CSV

Example content:

```
"No.", "Time", "Source", "Destination", ..., "value", ...
"1", "0.000000", "ABBMEDIU_...", "...", "350997, -611364, 533608, ..."
...
```

For best results, only export one stream. Otherwise, use built-in conversion.

6.6.3 How to Export

1. In Wireshark: set decoding to PhsMeas, see figure 39.
2. Export as CSV, see figure 40.

6.6.4 MAT File

Must contain variable `y`, matrix of size $N \times M$, where each column is a waveform.

6.6.5 PCAP or PCAPNG File

Captured using Wireshark [13]. Convert with `tshark` via the GUI.

Figure 39: How to convert .pcap file to .csv in Wireshark. Decoding SV streams.

6.7 Results Format of the GUI

Results are saved in the input file's directory:

- Figures: `.fig`
- Output: `.mat`, includes:
 - `D0main` – amplitudes/phases
 - `D0spectrum` – spectrum
 - `DI` – input quantities
 - `y` – waveform samples

`D0main{j, k}` is result for waveform j and section k . Follows QWTB [10] format.

6.8 Webpage with help for the GUI

The help for the GUI is available using shortened address <https://tinyurl.com/digitalITgui>.

Figure 40: How to convert .pcap file to .csv in Wireshark. Saving as .csv.

References

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21NRM02

Appendix A A2.2.1 report – questionnaire

A2.2.1 report

Czech Metrology Institute, LeftRight

June 29, 2023

Version: 1.0

digital-IT

Abstract

This document describes results of activity A2.2.1 of project 21NRM02 Digital-IT. The activity description is:

CMI and LeftRight, in consultation with VSL and VTT, will define the static, dynamic, linear and non-linear parameters that need to be estimated from CT and VT SV data streams (including amplitude, phase, frequency, harmonics and PQ parameters). CMI and LeftRight, in consultation with VSL and VTT, will also define optimisation criteria for either using existing SV data processing schemes or for the development of new data processing schemes that are able to cope with signal parameter requirements on expected grid signals (i.e. for specific parameters, specific disturbances or their combination) Input from the project's Stakeholder Committee (A4.1.2) will be sought.

1 Standards

Stand-alone Merging Units (SAMU) are standardized in IEC 61869-13:2021 [1]. More standards related to the topic are summarized in chapter 6.

Unfortunately the standards does not describes parameters nor quantities that are to be estimated from sampled values.

Without doubts typical power and power quality quantities as voltage, current and power are being evaluated. That means its amplitude, phase and frequency (also for harmonics).

Up to it, standard [1] defines testing of the SAMU, that hints some quantities to be obtained from sampled values. The tests defines a needs for standard quantities (amplitude and phase for harmonics), however clause 7.2.6.1301 of [1] defines test based on measuring time constant.

2 Questionnaire

A questionnaire has been sent to Stakeholders to find out real requirements of the SAMU users. The text of the questionnaire is shown in appendix B.

Contacted stakeholders:

<i>Stakeholder</i>	<i>Contacted by</i>	<i>Response</i>
Comsensus	Rado Lapuh	not yet
IskraEmeco	Rado Lapuh	not yet
Nathalie Baumier, RTE	Rado Lapuh	not yet
Goran Ericsson, SVK	Rado Lapuh	not yet
Kimmo Muttonen, FINGRID	Rado Lapuh	not yet
Peter Menke, Siemens	Rado Lapuh	yes
Christian Guibout	Martin Šíra	not yet
Volker Leitloff	Martin Šíra	not yet
Filippo Frugoni	Martin Šíra	yes
Paolo Mazza	Martin Šíra	not yet
Ashok Ganesh	Martin Šíra	not yet
Erik Schenkel	Martin Šíra	not yet
Imre Tannemaat, TenneT	Martin Šíra	yes
Jacques van Ammers	Martin Šíra	not yet
Václav Prokop, ABB Czech	Martin Šíra	yes
Václav Marcol, KPB Intra	Martin Šíra	yes
Marc Achterkamp	Martin Šíra	not yet
Wolfram Teppan, LEM	Martin Šíra	yes
Petri Hovila	Martin Šíra	not yet
Frej Suomi, ABB Finland	Martin Šíra	yes

3 Questionnaire Responses

3.1 Peter Menke

Cannot fill in the questionnaire because their portfolio still does not cover such a type of device.

3.2 Filippo Frugoni

Promised a reply, but the reply was not received.

3.3 Imre Tannemaat, TenneT

The filled questionnaire is in annex [D](#).

3.4 Václav Prokop, ABB Czech

Cannot fill in the questionnaire because their portfolio still does not cover such a type of device.

3.5 Václav Marcol, KPB Intra

Desiring cooperation, but cannot contribute to the questionnaire because only starting development in this field.

3.6 Wolfram Teppan, LEM

Only email reply was received. The following paragraph contains the important part of the email.

...I know that extensions of PQ algorithms to include perturbations up to 150 kHz are under discussion. The sampling rate of 96 kHz for DC will not be sufficient for this application. Further, there are discussions about DC PQ, but I do not know about additional requirements with respect to AC PQ. What I also heard are ideas for DC measurements with much higher bandwidth, but I'm not sure if this will influence DC ITs in the foreseeable future...

3.7 Frej Suomi, ABB Finland

The filled questionnaire is in annex [C](#).

4 Questionnaire Responses overview

Only 50 % of contacts replied. Two filled questionnaire were received and one short reply.

The important notes from questionnaire: Concerning the quantities:

- DC transients can occur and have to be represented according IEC61869-13. This implies the bandwidth of the devices has to be tested correctly.
- Quality bits should be considered in the data processing algorithms.
- For the future the algorithms should be able to work with frequencies up to 150 kHz.

Concerning the evaluation based on the estimated quantities:

- stability of the grid,
- power quality,
- asymmetry between phases for both voltage and current,
- line or cable impedances,
- voltage fluctuations over time.

Time critical is only the grid protection:

- at medium voltage, algorithm upper time limit 25 ms for fast protection.
- at high voltage, faster requirements should be met.

5 Conclusion

A questionnaire was prepared and sent to the interested parties. A handful of responses were evaluated.

Concerning the algorithms, a special care should be taken with the quality bits. Also, the bandwidth of the device plays a key role when evaluating the DC transients and should be considered for data processing.

The data evaluated from the quantities estimated by SAMU is similar to the use of Power Quality meters.

Processing time limitation is important for grid protection, but not for other kind of evaluation.

Thus, the parameters to be estimated from the data streams are:

- amplitude, phase, frequency and harmonics of the voltage and current,
- active, reactive and apparent power,
- DC transients.

While most of the parameters can be evaluated using available algorithms, publicly available algorithms for DC transients is missing. Up to it, the available algorithms have to be modified to take care of the quality bits.

References

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6 Appendixes

A VTT Review

Standards relevant to Sampled Values (SV) data transmission on a digital substation

Tapio Lehtonen, VTT Oy, Finland, tapio.lehtonen@vtt.fi

Relevant standards

For SAMUs and digital output ITs, the standards to refer to are:

IEC 61850-9-2	Sampled values over ISO/IEC 8802-3
IEC 61850-9-2 LE	Guideline to implementing IEC 61850-9-2
IEC 61869-1:2007	Instrument transformers - General requirements
IEC 61869-6:2016	Additional general requirements
IEC 61869-7 (NP)	Specific requirements for electronic Voltage Transformers, new work proposal, very early
IEC 61869-8 (CD)	Specific requirements for electronic Current Transformers, committee draft, most likely final
IEC 61869-9:2016	Digital interface for instrument transformers
IEC 61869-13:2021	Stand-alone merging unit (SAMU)

SV transmission in IEC 61850 and IEC 61869 series

Mapping of sampled value class model in IEC 61850-7-2 to Ethernet (ISO/IEC 8802-3) is defined in IEC 61850-9-2. Implementation specifics are left outside of the standard. A guideline for implementing the standard is published by UCA International User Group (IUG) under designation IEC 61850-9-2 LE. The guideline specifies sample rates for 50 Hz and 60 Hz systems, requirements for timing accuracy and other timing aspects, and specifics of data formatting inside the SV frames.

IEC TC 38 have adopted the concept of SV data transmission in IEC 61869-9 "Digital interface" for measurement equipment. IEC 61869-9 defines new sample rates, which can be found in the table below together with the old, deprecated ones from IEC 61850.9.2 LE.

Sample rate [Hz]	ASDUs per frame	Frame publishing rate [frames / s]	samples per nominal cycle		Remarks
			50 Hz	60 Hz	
4000	1	4000	80		protection application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 50 Hz systems
4800	1	4800		80	protection application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 60 Hz systems
4800	2	2400	96	80	Preferred rate for protection applications
5760	1	5760		96	60 Hz systems
12800	8	1600	256		measuring application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 50 Hz systems
14400	6	2400	288	240	Preferred rate for measuring applications
15360	8	1920		256	measuring application rate from IEC 61850-9-2LE for 60 Hz systems
96000	1	96000			Preferred rate for high bandwidth DC application

Performance requirements in IEC 61869 series

The SAMU standard IEC 61869-13 inherits performance requirements from IEC 61869-6. It also supplements the standard by introducing a higher accuracy class for a SAMU (measuring class 0,05) in support of the most accurate IT and LPIT measurement classes.

The following graph describes the dependence of the standard series with regards to digital output devices:

Stand-alone merging unit

Accuracy classes and requirements for measurement class SAMUs

SAMU accuracy classes for measuring voltage channels in IEC 61869-13:

- Accuracy required down to 20% of nominal input voltage
- Between 2 % and 20 % the error limits are double

Accuracy class	Voltage ratio error [%]	Phase error [min]
0,05	0.05	2.5
0,1	0.1	5
0,2	0.2	10
0,5	0.5	20
1,0	1.0	40

Limits of ratio error and phase displacement for current channels of measuring class SAMUs in IEC 61869-13:

Class	Ratio error limit [%]				Phase displacement [min]				Phase displacement [deg]			
	% of rated current				% of rated current				% of rated current			
	$K_{imin} / 4$	K_{imin}	100	K_{imax}	$K_{imin} / 4$	K_{imin}	100	K_{imax}	$K_{imin} / 4$	K_{imin}	100	K_{imax}
0,05	0.1	0.05	0.05	0.05	6	2.5	2.5	2.5	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0
0,1	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	10	5	5	5	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1
0,2	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.2	20	10	10	10	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2
0,5	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	60	30	30	30	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5
1	2	1	1	1	120	60	60	60	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

Accuracy classes and requirements for measurement class instrument transformers

Limits of ratio error and phase displacement for measuring class voltage LPITs in IEC 61869-7:

Class	Ratio error limit [%]			Phase displacement [min]			Phase displacement [deg]		
	% of rated voltage			% of rated voltage			% of rated voltage		
	80	100	120	80	100	120	80	100	120
0,1	0.1	0.1	0.1	5	5	5	0.08	0.08	0.08
0,2	0.2	0.2	0.2	10	10	10	0.17	0.17	0.17
0,5	0.5	0.5	0.5	20	20	20	0.33	0.33	0.33
1	1	1	1	40	40	40	0.67	0.67	0.67

Limits of ratio error and phase displacement for measuring class current LPITs in IEC 61869-8:

Class	Ratio error limit [%]					Phase displacement [min]					Phase displacement [deg]				
	% of rated current					% of rated current					% of rated current				
	1	5	20	100	120	1	5	20	100	120	1	5	20	100	120
0,1	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.1		15	8	5	5		0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	
0,2	0.75	0.35	0.2	0.2		30	15	10	10		0.5	0.3	0.2	0.2	
0,2S	0.75	0.35	0.2	0.2	0.2	30	15	10	10	10	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.2	0.2
0,5	1.5	0.75	0.5	0.5		90	45	30	30		1.5	0.8	0.5	0.5	
0,5S	1.5	0.75	0.5	0.5	0.5	90	45	30	30	30	1.5	0.8	0.5	0.5	0.5
1	3	1.5	1	1		180	90	60	60		3.0	1.5	1.0	1.0	

Ratio error and phase displacement for harmonic frequencies

Accuracy requirements for harmonic frequencies for measuring class SAMUs and instrument transformers are given in IEC 61869-13 and IEC 61869-6. Class 0,05 is only applicable to SAMUs.

Class	Ratio error limit [%]								Phase displacement [degrees]									
	0 Hz		1 Hz		Harmonic component						1 Hz		Harmonic component					
					1st	2nd to 4th	5th to 6th	7th to 9th	10th to 13th	>= 13th			1st	2nd to 4th	5th to 6th	7th to 9th	10th to 13th	
0,05	+0.5 -100	+0.5 -30	0.05	0.5	1	2	4	+4 -100	45	0.04	0.5	1	2	4				
0,1	+1 -100	+1 -30	0.1	1	2	4	8	+8 -100	45	0.1	1	2	4	8				
0,2; 0,2S	+2 -100	+2 -30	0.2	2	4	8	16	+16 -100	45	0.2	2	4	8	16				
0,5; 0,5S	+5 -100	+5 -30	0.5	5	10	20	20	+20 -100	45	0.5	5	10	20	20				
1	+10 -100	+10 -30	1	10	20	20	20	+20 -100	45	1.0	10	20	20	20				

Combining instrument transformer and SAMU accuracy classes

When a current or voltage output instrument transformer is connected to a SAMU, the combined accuracy class is given by

$$C_{\text{COMB}} = \sqrt{C_{\text{IT}}^2 + C_{\text{SAMU}}^2}$$

The overall accuracy for different combinations is then (from IEC 61869-13):

SAMU \ IT	0,1	0,2	0,5	1,0	3,0 VT only
0,05	0,1 (0,112)	0,2 (0,206)	0,5 (0,503)	1,0 (1,001)	3,0 (3,000)
0,1	0,2 (0,141)	0,2 (0,224)	0,5 (0,510)	1,0 (1,005)	3,0 (3,002)
0,2	0,2 (0,224)	0,5 (0,283)	0,5 (0,539)	1,0 (1,020)	3,0 (3,007)
0,5	0,5 (0,510)	0,5 (0,539)	1,0 (0,707)	1,0 (1,118)	3,0 (3,041)
1,0	1,0 (1,005)	1,0 (1,020)	1,0 (1,118)	3,0 (1,414)	3,0 (3,162)

B Questionnaire

Questionnaire for the Digital-IT project - data processing and uncertainty estimation part

The project *Digital-IT: Metrology for digital substation instrumentation* is focused on development of the metrology infrastructure for the traceable measurement and calibration of digital substation instrumentation. That is Sampled Values (SV) enabled equipment such as Stand Alone Merging Units (SAMUs), digital instrument transformers and instrument transformer measuring bridges.

One of the specific objectives of the project is to develop software for controlling the setups and handling of SV data streams and develop new data processing and uncertainty estimation approaches for new data rates up to 96000 Samples per second.

Concerning the data processing and uncertainty estimation approaches, it would be helpful to collect user demands based on the practical needs. Your answers will be considered with outmost importance, as they will help us to optimize our steps in this specific part of the project.

We are considering developing estimation of the following quantities and parameters:

Quantity	Parameters
Voltage	amplitude, phase, frequency, harmonics
Current	amplitude, phase, frequency, harmonics
Power	active power, reactive power, apparent power

For the optimal software development, we would welcome answers on the following questions:

Question 1:

What additional quantities and associated signal parameters (including Power Quality parameters) do you expect to evaluate from data (SV) using SAMU? *We ask so we know which algorithms we need to develop and/or apply.*

Your answer here...

Question 2:

What do you want to evaluate from quantities and parameters? How do you use the quantities and parameters further? *We ask so we could properly select the best data processing algorithms for a particular quantity/parameter.*

Your answer here...

Question 3:

What is your expected estimation time of quantities or parameters in real time processing? *We ask because we need to know limits for computational complexity and because for someone a real time response is sufficient in milliseconds, for others in seconds.*

Your answer here...

C Questionnaire reply by Suomi, ABB Finland

Questionnaire for the Digital-IT project - data processing and uncertainty estimation part

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For the optimal software development, we would welcome answers on the following questions:

Question 1:

What additional quantities and associated signal parameters (including Power Quality parameters) do you expect to evaluate from data (SV) using SAMU? *We ask so we know which algorithms we need to develop and/or apply.*

During close or open operations some "DC transients" can occur and these needs to be represented correctly according to IEC61869-13 minimum transient performance requirements to have differential current protection working correctly. Fast differential protection uses only a few samples, which requires that low pass cutoff (-3dB) frequency must not be above 1 Hz. Slower differential current protection can use FFT which do not care about DC component correctness that heavily, the measuring input may however not magnetically saturate during this "DC transient", magnetic saturation (even minimal saturation) distorts the AC waveform and thereby also the phase angle.

This is the reason behind IEC61869-13 requiring 1Hz-3dB point and the TPM classes based on "instantaneous alternating error component" (note DC error is allowed but AC error has tight limits)

Additionally, the detailed quality bits of the SV channels should be considered when evaluating SAMU or MU performance.

709 The use of the quality attributes for SV is limited and detailed by IEC 61869-9:2016 as shown
710 in Table 10.

711 **Table 10 – Limitation of quality attributes according to IEC 61869-9:2016**

detailQual	Validity			restricted use in IEC61869-9:2016
	good	questionable	invalid	
	X			
overflow				Set to "false" (not used in 61689-9:2016)
outOfRange		x		"true"/"false" (Used for Clipping)
badReference				Set to "false" (not used in 61689-9:2016)
oscillatory				Set to "false" (not used in 61689-9:2016)
failure			x	"true"/"false" (Used for any kind of HW-Supervision...)

oldData				Set to "false" (not used in 61689-9:2016)
inconsistent				Set to "false" (not used in 61689-9:2016)
inaccurate		x		"true"/"false" ("false" if SV may not meet nameplate accuracy)

712

713 As shown in Table 10, only 3 different values of DA detailQual are applicable to SV according
714 to IEC 61869-9:2016 (subclause 6.903.9). All other possible values of detailQual according to
715 the definition in IEC 61850-7-2:2010+AMD1 are not used for SV. The values of detailed qualities
716 represented by the DA detailQual used are:

- 717 • SV with the validity "good" fulfils the accuracy given in the nameplate of the merging
718 unit.
- 719 • SV with the validity "questionable" and the detailed quality "inaccurate" indicate that SV
720 does not meet the nameplate accuracy. Typical reasons could be problems with the
721 calibration or DC-offset.
- 722 • SV with the validity "questionable" and the detailed quality "outOfRange" indicate a
723 clipping of the merging unit. The SV in this case are still the merging unit's best estimate
724 of the primary value and not set to zero for instance.
- 725 • SV with the validity "invalid" indicates a serious problem in the Merging Unit.

726 If the validity is non-nominal, i.e. "Questionable" or "Invalid", the receiving IED need to forward
727 the quality attributes to the connected protection functions. Different ways to react are possible,
728 depending on the application. The expected behaviour of different protection functions in case

Question 2:

What do you want to evaluate from quantities and parameters? How do you use the quantities and parameters further? *We ask so we could properly select the best data processing algorithms for a particular quantity/parameter.*

Various protection and measuring algorithms based on amplitudes, phase, harmonics (both phase and amplitude) and frequency.

Question 3:

What is your expected estimation time of quantities or parameters in real time processing? *We ask because we need to know limits for computational complexity and because for someone a real time response is sufficient in milliseconds, for others in seconds.*

For medium voltage grid protection purposes the algorithms upper time limit is around 20-25 ms for fast protection. This is enough time to do FFT of the whole fundamental frequency period. There are however also instantaneous overcurrent protection that uses peak to peak algorithm which can be faster than FFT. High voltage protection algorithms can have even faster requirements, e.g. acting on only a few SV samples.

D Questionnaire reply by Tannemaat, TenneT

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One of the specific objectives of the project is to develop software for controlling the setups and handling of SV data streams and develop new data processing and uncertainty estimation approaches for new data rates up to 96000 Samples per second.

Concerning the data processing and uncertainty estimation approaches, it would be helpful to collect user demands based on the practical needs. Your answers will be considered with utmost importance, as they will help us to optimize our steps in this specific part of the project.

We are considering developing estimation of the following quantities and parameters:

Quantity	Parameters
Voltage	amplitude, phase, frequency, harmonics
Current	amplitude, phase, frequency, harmonics
Power	active power, reactive power, apparent power

For the optimal software development, we would welcome answers on the following questions:

Question 1:

What additional quantities and associated signal parameters (including Power Quality parameters) do you expect to evaluate from data (SV) using SAMU? *We ask so we know which algorithms we need to develop and/or apply.*

Answer: The table provides all relevant values for a single phase current voltage and/or power. So for this purpose the table seems complete.

Question 2:

What do you want to evaluate from quantities and parameters? How do you use the quantities and parameters further? *We ask so we could properly select the best data processing algorithms for a particular quantity/parameter.*

Answer: Now, if all the quantities from the table are available with good time precision (and location of measurement) there are many aspects that are interesting to analyze:

- 1. Voltage and frequency stability of the grid*
- 2. Power quality monitoring*
- 3. Asymmetry of currents and voltages between phases (by comparing the values between phases. This is relevant for balancing studies and can be used as input for studies that focus on interference of other (third party) systems.*
- 4. Line (or cable) impedances of the connection between two points. This can be used to improve models for the calculation of power flows, short circuit currents, etc.*

5. *Voltage fluctuation over time. With smart algorithms the actual short circuit level can be estimated, enabling a system operator to reconfigure the network (switching actions / change tap positions of power transformers) to adjust the actual short circuit level.*
6. *Etc.*

Question 3:

What is your expected estimation time of quantities or parameters in real time processing? *We ask because we need to know limits for computational complexity and because for someone a real time response is sufficient in milliseconds, for others in seconds.*

Answer: Most of the items in Q2 are not critical in terms of time, except if they are used to operate the system. Since it is not used as such at the moment we cannot provide the required processing time. Except for protection application (processing asap) the requested processing time will probably not be under 1s.

21NRM02

Appendix B Resampling using Upsampling - Filtering - Decimation approach (UFD)

Resampling the SV data stream

Aleksander Lisowiec, Jerzy Chudorlinski

Łukasiewicz - ITR

Resampling here will be presented in the context of substation automation according to IEC 61850 standard where data is in the form of SV stream of line voltages and currents which are periodic functions of time. In this context resampling might be necessary for at least two reasons.

1. The sampling of voltage and current signals is not coherent, which means that the sampling frequency f_s is not a whole multiple of power line frequency f_{line} . In that case the number of samples per period, SPP , is not a whole number which leads to spectrum leakage when applying DFT to data stream. This is a common situation as f_{line} is usually not exactly equal to $f_{linenom} = 50$ Hz (or 60 Hz). Coherent sampling can only be achieved in laboratory setup.

2. There is a need to lower data rate. This may be the case when voltage and current signals are sampled at 96 kHz but some IEDs determine the signal spectrum with the use of FFT so SPP should be a whole power of 2. As will be shown later, resampling is not a computationally intensive process so it might be rational to reduce sampling rate and then compute the spectrum by FFT.

Resampling technique, when applied to data stream at constant rate f_s such as SV, results in a new data stream at a rate $(N/M) \cdot f_s$ where N and M are whole numbers called respectively the interpolation and decimation coefficients. When the aim of resampling is to restore the SV data rate to nominal value, SPP_{nom} , which is 80 or 256 as defined by IEC 61850-9-2LE, M and N coefficients are close to each other. When the aim is to lower the data rate, M is greater than N .

The resampling procedure, Fig. 1, consists of three operations. In the upsampling operation $N-1$ zero samples are inserted between each pair of the original data. In the interpolation operation the resulting stream is passed through the interpolation low pass filter. The decimation operation consists of taking every M -th sample at the output of the interpolation filter. The role of the interpolation filter which will be further called the resample filter is twofold. First it produces interpolated values between each original data points and second it restricts the bandwidth of the upsampled signal to prevent the spectrum aliasing [1,2]. How the signal spectra at various stages of the resampling process change and how the N and M coefficients determine the resample filter bandwidth can be found in reference works [1,2].

Fig. 1 Block diagram of the resampling process

The ideal resample filter should have a flat pass band up to the highest frequency component of the signal and sufficient attenuation at $(N/(2M)) \cdot f_s$ (with the assumption $M \geq N$) to prevent spectrum aliasing [1,2].

Though in principle resampling can generate a data rate arbitrary close to coherent sampling, albeit at the cost of growing N and M , there are practical considerations limiting the resampling resolution accuracy like uncertainty in f_{line} determination

Determination of N and M coefficients

As the reason to resample SV data stream is to reduce the spectrum leakage when using DFT, the question arises how the relative difference of SPP from the whole number of samples per period affects the accuracy of spectrum determination. The relationship between the relative error in fundamental harmonic amplitude determination (for which we write $errA1$ from now on) and the relative deviation of the number of samples per period from the nominal value, $\delta SPP = (SPP - SPP_{nom})/SPP_{nom}$, for small values of δSPP , can be expressed by the following formula

$$errA1 = k \cdot \delta SPP. \quad (1)$$

The linear relationship between $errA1$ and δSPP is valid over $\delta SPP \in \langle -0.02, 0.02 \rangle$. The k coefficient is equal to -0.5 and it has been obtained empirically by calculating the DFT of a sinusoidal signal of varying frequency sampled at a constant rate.

Formula(1) is the basis, or at least a starting point, for the determination of the resampling process parameters N and M . As $M \cong N$ or $M > N$, it is better, considering the resolution of resampling procedure, to vary M with varying f_{line} and keep the N constant. The value of M , for which SPP best approximates SPP_{nom} , for given f_{line} and N , is computed from the formula

$$M = round \left(\frac{N \cdot f_s}{f_{line} \cdot SPP_{nom}} \right). \quad (2)$$

The value of M computed for $f_{line} = f_{linenom}$ will be further denoted by M_{nom} .

δSPP can be expressed by the following relationship

$$\delta SPP = \frac{\frac{N}{M} \cdot \frac{f_s}{f_{line}} - SPP_{nom}}{SPP_{nom}}. \quad (3)$$

If we denote by M_{exact} the exact number (generally not a whole one) for which $(N/M_{exact}) \cdot (f_s/f_{line}) = SPP_{nom}$ and observe that $M = M_{exact} + x$ for some x in the interval $\langle -0.5, 0.5 \rangle$, (3) can be transformed as follows

$$\delta SPP = \frac{\frac{N}{M_{exact} + x} \cdot \frac{M_{exact}}{N} \cdot SPP_{nom} - SPP_{nom}}{SPP_{nom}} = \frac{M_{exact}}{M_{exact} + x} - 1, \quad (4)$$

and taking into account that $M_{exact} \gg 1$,

$$|\delta SPP| \approx \left| \frac{x}{M} \right|. \quad (5)$$

$|\delta SPP|$ attains the largest value when $x = \pm 0.5$, so

$$|\delta SPP| \leq \left| \frac{1}{2 \cdot M} \right|. \quad (6)$$

Equations (1) and (6) can be used to determine the resampling parameters N and M needed to keep the error $errA1$, due to leakage, within prescribed limit. As f_{line} is usually very close to $f_{linenom}$, M does not change much around M_{nom} so the M_{nom} can be obtained from (6). For example, if we want to limit to 50 ppm the contribution of δSPP to $errA1$, we get from (1) that $\delta SPP < 10^{-4}$ and substituting this into (6) we obtain that $M_{nom} \geq 5000$. If $SPP_{nom} = (f_s/f_{line})$ which is a typical case in IEC 61850 substation automation, N is then equal to M_{nom} . Generally if a new nominal number of samples per line period is required, SPP_{nomnew} , a formula below should be used

$$N = M_{nom} \cdot SPP_{nomnew} \cdot \frac{f_s}{f_{line}}. \quad (7)$$

Keeping N constant, the value of M for each value of f_{line} is next computed by formula (2). Figure 2 shows the values of M for f_{line} changing over the range <49 Hz, 51 Hz>, with $N = 5000$, $f_s = 12800$ and $SPP_{nom} = 256$.

Fig. 2 Range of change of M for $f_{line} \in \langle 49 \text{ Hz}, 51 \text{ Hz} \rangle$

Resample filter design

Having obtained the values of N and M coefficients, the next step is to design the resample filter. This is a low pass FIR filter with the passband extending up to the highest frequency component of the signal and stopband starting at $(N/(2M)) \cdot f_s$. If the value of N is held constant, a single resample filter is needed, designed with the maximum value of M , M_{max} , computed at $f_{line} = f_{linemin}$. An example of such a filter computed with the use of **fir1** and **kaiseroid** GNU Octave functions has been shown in Figure 3. The parameters to the mentioned GNU Octave functions were $M = M_{max} = 5102$, $f_s = 12800$, $N = 5000$ and the passband width 2200 Hz. These functions need additionally as parameters a passband ripple which was set to 0.0001% and a stopband attenuation which was set to 40 dB. The length L of the computed filter is 122664. Various tools besides GNU Octave can be used to design such filter [3].

Fig. 3 Resample filter designed with fir1 and kaiseroid GNU Octave functions

The passband ripple of the filter determines how faithfully the original waveform of the signal is reproduced after the resampling procedure. With the accuracy target equal to 50 ppm the passband ripple should be no larger than 0.0001%.

The length of the resample filter depends on N and M but also, quite dramatically, on the width of the transition band of the filter. The closer the passband edge is to the Nyquist frequency $(N/(2M)) \cdot f_s$, the longer is the filter. Fig. 4 presents the length of the resample filter computed with fir1 and kaiseroid as a function of the of the passband width. The parameters to the GNU Octave functions were $M = 5001$, $f_s = 12800$, $N = 5000$, passband ripple equal to 0.0001% and a stopband attenuation equal to 40 dB.

Fig. 4 Number of resample filter coefficients as a function of the passband width; $N=5000$, $M=5001$, $f_s=12800$, passband ripple = 0.0001%, stopband attenuation = 40 dB; Nyquist frequency is equal to 6400 Hz

Though the length L of the resampling filter may be quite large, the number of multiplications and summations to compute each sample of the resampled stream is the length of the filter divided by N . The total number of multiplications and summations to compute SPP_{nom} samples is thus $(L/N) \cdot Spp_{nom}$, which for the example filter from Fig. 3 is equal to 6400.

Noise

As follows from the above, the resampling procedure is low pass filtering. The resample filter is of FIR type which is quite insensitive to roundoff errors. If there is a need to filter out the unwanted noise, the bandwidth of the resample filter can be reduced below the highest frequency signal component. In this respect resampling is very robust when it comes to noise immunity.

Resampling procedure design algorithm

The steps that have to be taken in the design of resampling algorithm have been presented in the following flowchart, Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Resample procedure design flowchart

Parameterization of the DC setting function

During some faults in power system, like for instance a short circuit across generator terminals [4], a decaying DC component may be present in a measured current signal. The amplitude and rate of DC component decay can give information about the nature of the fault. The DC component, together with sinusoidal component is modeled by the equation (8) and the aim is to parameterize the model, i.e., find the values of I_{sc} , τ , I_0 , f and φ_0 , given the signal samples.

$$i(t) = I_{sc} \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} + I_0 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_0) \quad (8)$$

One method that works well is the nonlinear regression. Many software mathematical packages offer functions for fitting models to data. MATLAB has a **fit** function, Mathematica has a **FindFit** and the equivalent function in Python scipy module is **curve_fit**. Here a **nonlin_curvefit** function from GNU Octave **optim** package has been used to fit data corrupted by Gaussian noise, (of zero mean and variance equal to 5% of the signal amplitude), to the model described by (8), Fig. 6.

Fig. 6 Fitting a sinusoid signal plus dc decaying component data with GNU Octave `nonlin_curvefit` function

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Appendix C Monte-Carlo based SV data parameter uncertainty estimation

Monte-Carlo based SV data parameter uncertainty estimation

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1 Description of the Monte-Carlo based simulator

The uncertainty analysis of the algorithms was performed using several Monte-Carlo simulations in Matlab software. The first important step is to generate the voltage and the current waveforms that are inputs for the algorithms. In our case we generated the voltage waveform using Eq. 1 and current waveform using Eq. 2. In principle both equations consist of fundamental voltage and the current, four additional harmonics that also need to be estimated by the algorithms. Additionally, both waveforms contain a few additional harmonic components having smaller amplitudes that act as disturbance for the algorithm. These spurious harmonics were randomly selected between 6th and 50th harmonic and the number of those spurious harmonics has been defined by the N_{harm} parameter (between 0 and 5). In addition to spurious harmonics, also a random noise has been added to the voltage and current waveform. The shape of the noise waveform for every simulation was always random. However, for noise waveforms we controlled the RMS value, and we checked that the DC value of the noise was practically zero.

$$\begin{aligned} U(t) = & U_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_1) + \\ & + U_{harm2} \cdot 0.01 \cdot U_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot 2 \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_2) + U_{harm3} \cdot 0.01 \cdot U_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot 3 \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_3) + \\ & + U_{harm4} \cdot 0.01 \cdot U_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot 4 \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_4) + U_{harm5} \cdot 0.01 \cdot U_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot 5 \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_5) + \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{harm}} U_{harm,i} \cdot 0.01 \cdot A_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot N \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_i) + \\ & + U_{noise} \cdot 0.01 \cdot U_1 \cdot rnd(t) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} I(t) = & I_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_6) + \\ & + I_{harm2} \cdot 0.01 \cdot I_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot 2 \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_7) + I_{harm3} \cdot 0.01 \cdot I_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot 3 \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_8) + \\ & + I_{harm4} \cdot 0.01 \cdot I_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot 4 \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_9) + I_{harm5} \cdot 0.01 \cdot I_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot 5 \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_{10}) + \\ & + \sum_{j=1}^{N_{harm}} I_{harm,j} \cdot 0.01 \cdot I_1 \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot N \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi_j) + \\ & + I_{noise} \cdot 0.01 \cdot I_1 \cdot rnd(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The simulator also considers the jitter effect, Eq. 3. In this case a small random deviation of the time has been added to the idea time vector. Again, the overall RMS value of the jitter can be controlled by $jitter_{RMS}$ parameter, the DC value of the time deviation is zero again, but otherwise, the variation is random. This time vector with jitter effect has been included for all parts of the waveform, *i.e.*, fundamental signal, harmonics, spurious harmonics and noise. However, for each simulation the same time vector has been used for voltage and current waveform generation (*i.e.*, we assume that the effect of jitter is the same when sampling voltage or current waveforms since sampling is performed at the same time).

$$t = t + jitter_{RMS} \cdot rnd(t) \quad (3)$$

It is evident that Eqs. 1-3 contains multiple parameters that can be generally divided into two groups. In the first group are parameters that are systematically varied and strictly tracked. Usually, they are the parameters that needs to be estimated by the algorithms. In the second group are the parameters that are randomly varied. Those parameters are changed for every Monte-Carlo simulation. On contrary, the systematically varied parameters are generally varied much less often and only when we want to change the parameter in a sensitivity analysis or when we want to perform another sensitivity analysis (more details are given below).

The systematically varied parameters are:

- N : Number of samples in the waveform (not directly shown in Eqs. 1-3).
- f_s : Sampling frequency (not directly shown in Eqs. 1-3).
- $jitter_{RMS}$: The RMS value of the jitter.
- U_{h2} : The voltage amplitude of the 2nd harmonic component given in % relative to the fundamental voltage.
- U_{h3} : The voltage amplitude of the 3rd harmonic component given in % relative to the fundamental voltage.
- U_{h4} : The voltage amplitude of the 4th harmonic component given in % relative to the fundamental voltage.
- U_{h5} : The voltage amplitude of the 5th harmonic component given in % relative to the fundamental voltage.
- U_h : The voltage amplitude of the spurious harmonic component (from 6th to 50th harmonic) given in % relative to the fundamental voltage. The U_h is a vector having a length of N_{harm} .
- U_{noise} : The RMS noise that is added to voltage waveform. The noise is given in % relative to the fundamental voltage.
- I_{h2} : The current amplitude of the 2nd harmonic component given in % relative to the fundamental current.
- I_{h3} : The current amplitude of the 3rd harmonic component given in % relative to the fundamental current.
- I_{h4} : The current amplitude of the 4th harmonic component given in % relative to the fundamental current.
- I_{h5} : The current amplitude of the 5th harmonic component given in % relative to the fundamental current.
- I_h : The current amplitude of the spurious harmonic component (from 6th to 50th harmonic) given in % relative to the fundamental current. The I_h is a vector having a length of N_{harm} .
- I_{noise} : The RMS noise that is added to current waveform. The noise is given in % relative to the fundamental current.
- N_{harm} : Number of spurious voltage and current harmonics components. The harmonic(s) are randomly chosen for each simulation between 6th to 50th harmonic. However, for the simulation the same harmonics are then applied to the voltage and current waveform.

All systematically varied parameters are listed in Table 1 where the origin value for each parameter is defined. The origin values are always used for all simulations except when a sensitivity analysis of a certain parameter is calculated. In this case the values shown in *Varied values* column are used for sensitivity analysis of parameter of interest while the others remain the same as shown in *Origin* column. More details are given below. Please note that origin values and varied values remain the same for all study algorithms. The only exceptions are parameters N and f_s which are slightly different for *Resampling* algorithm and other algorithms.

Table 1: The list of systematically varied parameters with corresponding origin value and the varied values that are used for sensitivity analysis.

Parameter (X)	Origin	Varied values	Units
N	20.000	10.000, 20.000, 50.000, 96.000 1.000, 2.000, 5.000, 10.000, 20.000, 50.000*	/
f_s	12.500 (12.800*)	4.000, 12.500, 96.000 4.000, 4.800, 12.800, 15.360, 96.000*	Hz
$jitter_{RMS}$	0	0, 10 ns, 100 ns, 1 μ s	s
U_{h2}	1	1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50	%
U_{h3}	1	1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50	%
U_{h4}	1	1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50	%
U_{h5}	1	1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50	%
U_h	0.01	0, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 2, 5	%
U_{noise}	10^{-6}	0, 10^{-6} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-1}	%
I_{h2}	1	1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50	%
I_{h3}	1	1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50	%
I_{h4}	1	1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50	%
I_{h5}	1	1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50	%
I_h	0.01	0, 0.01, 0.1, 1, 2, 5	%
I_{noise}	10^{-6}	0, 10^{-6} , 10^{-3} , 10^{-2} , 10^{-1}	%
N_{harm}	1	0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5	/

* Resampling algorithm

Another group of parameters are randomly varied parameters. The parameters are:

- f : Frequency of the fundamental signal. The frequency for each simulation has been randomly varied between $\pm 1\%$ from nominal 50 Hz.
- $\varphi_1 - \varphi_{10}$: Phases of the fundamental signal and harmonics (2nd to 5th) for the voltage and current waveforms.
- φ_i : Phases of the spurious voltage harmonic components. This is a vector with a length of N_{harm} where each component is individually randomly defined.
- φ_j : Phases of the spurious current harmonic components. This is a vector with a length of N_{harm} where each component is individually randomly defined.
- t : Time vector is randomly changed for each simulation according to jitter value.

Table 2: The list of randomly varied parameters with corresponding variation range.

Parameter (R)	Range
f	49.5 to 50.5 Hz
$\varphi_1 - \varphi_{10}$	$-\pi$ to $+\pi$
φ_i	$-\pi$ to $+\pi$
φ_j	$-\pi$ to $+\pi$
t	random

All randomly varied parameters are listed in Table 2 where the variation ranges are also defined. In addition to systematically and randomly varied parameter we had also two constants U_1 and I_1 which are the voltage and the current of the fundamental signal. Those value remained the same for all simulations, *i.e.* $U_1 = 100$ V and $I_1 = 5$ A, respectively.

The generated voltage and current waveforms (Eqs. 1-3) act as in input for the five examined algorithms (Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample, Windowed). The algorithms return the following estimated parameters:

- f : Frequency of the fundamental signal.

- U_1 : Voltage of the fundamental signal.
- U_{h2} : The voltage amplitude of the 2nd harmonic component.
- U_{h3} : The voltage amplitude of the 3rd harmonic component.
- U_{h4} : The voltage amplitude of the 4th harmonic component.
- U_{h5} : The voltage amplitude of the 5th harmonic component.
- I_1 : Current of the fundamental signal.
- I_{h2} : The current amplitude of the 2nd harmonic component.
- I_{h3} : The current amplitude of the 3rd harmonic component.
- I_{h4} : The current amplitude of the 4th harmonic component.
- I_{h5} : The current amplitude of the 5th harmonic component.
- φ : Phase difference between fundamental voltage and current.
- P : Active power of the fundamental signal (without harmonics).
- S : Apparent power of the fundamental signal (without harmonics).

All estimated values are always given in SI units (*i.e.*, Hz, V, A, W and VA). Generally, all algorithms estimate all 14 parameters. The only exception is Windowed algorithms which only estimates U_1 , I_1 , φ , P and S (Table 3).

Table 3: The list of examined algorithms and estimated parameters. The symbols \surd and \times denotes which algorithm can estimated which parameter.

Estimated parameter (Y)	Aspline	Aftw	AMHFE	Resample	Windowed
f	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times
U_1	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd
U_{h2}	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times
U_{h3}	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times
U_{h4}	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times
U_{h5}	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times
I_1	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd
I_{h2}	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times
I_{h3}	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times
I_{h4}	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times
I_{h5}	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\times
φ	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd
P	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd
S	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd	\surd

Several systematically and randomly varied parameters, five examined algorithms and a number of estimated parameters are quite high therefore analysis with systematic approach would be very time consuming and would need high computational requirements. Moreover, a large amount of data would be quite difficult to analyse. Therefore, in our approach we decided for sensitivity analysis where we observe how each systematically varied parameter influences the uncertainty of each estimated parameter for each examined algorithm.

The sensitivity analysis contains three loops, Fig. 1. For one sensitivity analysis (Fig. 1, green loop) only one systematically varied parameter (Fig. 1, X_i) is changed using the varied values from Table 1, while the other systematically varied parameters (Fig. 1, $X_1 - X_{16}$, without X_i) remain at origin values from Table 1. For each value of systematically varied parameter of interest X_i (*i.e.*, each combination) 50.000 Monte-Carlo simulations (blue loop) were performed and for each simulation each randomly varied parameter (Fig. 1, $R_1 - R_{14}$) has been randomly changed. After obtaining the results from algorithms (Fig. 1, $Y_1 - Y_{14}$) we track the maximal difference between all input and output variables and after completing 50.000 simulations we obtained the overall maximal error (*i.e.*, the uncertainty of the algorithms, Fig. 1, $UNC_1 - UNC_{14}$). After completing the variation

of all values of systematically varied parameter of interest X_i (Fig. 1, green loop) one sensitivity analysis is completed. To obtain all sensitivity analysis all systematically varied parameters need to be analysed using the same procedure (Fig. 1, red loop).

As a result, the red loop needs to be repeated 16 times which is the total number of systematically varied parameters X , green loop needs to be repeated 3-6 times depending on the number of varied values for each systematically varied parameters X_i and the blue loop is repeated 50.000 times to reliably obtain the maximal errors.

With this analysis we obtained 1.120 dependencies as 14 estimated parameters, 5 algorithms and 16 systematically varied parameters were included in the analysis (note that Windowed algorithm does not estimate all parameters therefore the number above is slightly lower than just a simple multiplication of the numbers given above).

Figure 1: The principle of sensitivity analysis for algorithm examination. The X denotes the systematically varied input parameters, R are randomly varied input parameters, Y are estimated parameters and UNC are the final uncertainties after completing all simulations.

2 Results

The results of the sensitivity analysis and corresponding uncertainties are shown in this chapter. The uncertainty for each estimated parameter and for each algorithm contains of two parts. The first part is the base accuracy which is desired to be as low as possible but on contrary it should already include at the most dependencies of systematically varied input parameters. On contrary, the uncertainties might sometimes significantly increase for some systematically varied input variable. In these cases, empirical equations have been fitted to simulated result. To obtain the final uncertainty for the estimated parameter all contributions should be summarised (*i.e.*, all dependencies defined by the empirical equations should be added the base accuracy of the algorithm). However, the empirical equation could be neglected if the value of systematically varied input parameters is smaller or equal to the origin value as shown in Table 1 since in this case the dependence is already included in the base accuracy of the algorithm. Two examples are given below.

The base accuracy might be relatively small, but these cases generally require the inclusion of more empirical equation and *vice versa*, sometimes the base accuracy might be already relatively high therefore only a few or no empirical equation needs to be included for final uncertainty calculation.

Below two uncertainty calculation examples, one can find 14 tables: one for each estimated parameter. Each table gather the base accuracies and all dependencies (*i.e.*, all empirical equations) for all five algorithms. The units of all uncertainties and units for all systematically varied input parameters are always given in a basic SI unit (*i.e.*, Hz, V, A, radians, W, VA)

Example 1: Uncertainty of frequency estimation for Aspline algorithm (Table 4)

Let assume that $U_{harm2} = 30$ V as estimated by the Aspline algorithm. The number of samples was 20.000. The SAMU specifications defines that the RSM jitter is 100 ns and the noise for $U_l = 100$ V signal is 10 mV. The uncertainty analysis shown below (Table 4) defines the following base accuracy and dependencies:

Base accuracy: 2.5 nHz

Dependencies:

$$UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 2.3 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm2}(\text{V})$$

$$UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 2.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$$

$$UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 9 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$$

$$UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot N \quad (N \text{ should be at least } 20.000)$$

To define each uncertainty contribution in SI units (*i.e.*, in Hz), the coefficient from the equation should be multiplied by a certain systematically varied parameter that is also given in SI units (*e.g.*, for the jitter a number $100 \cdot 10^{-9}$ (*i.e.*, 100 ns) needs to be multiplied by 9 which correspond to 900 nHz uncertainty contribution). The uncertainty contributions for the frequency estimations for Aspline algorithm are therefore 2.5 nHz for base accuracy, 690 nHz is a contribution due to U_{harm2} , 2.6 μ Hz due to the RMS noise and 900 nHz due to the jitter. The contribution of N could be neglected since N is higher or equal to 20.000. The final uncertainty of frequency estimation of Aspline algorithm is thus 4.215 μ Hz which is the sum of all contributions.

Example 2: Uncertainty of the amplitude of the second voltage harmonic estimation (U_{h2}) for AMHFE algorithm (Table 6).

The AMHFE algorithm estimated that $U_1 = 100$ V. By experiences it is known that the amplitude of spurious harmonics and noise are $U_h = 7$ mV and $U_{noise} = 100$ mV, respectively. In the specifications of the SAMU it is specified that the jitter is 10 ns. The sampling frequency is 12.500.

The second uncertainty analysis shown below (Table 6) defines the following base accuracy and dependencies:

Base accuracy: $0.2 \mu\text{V} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$

Dependencies:

$$UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 7.2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$$

$$UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$$

$$UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 680 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{V})$$

$$UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 5.8 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$$

The uncertainty contributions for the second voltage harmonic estimation (U_{h2}) for AMHFE algorithm are therefore 20 μV for base accuracy, 5.04 μV due to the U_{harm} , 3.2 mV due to U_{noise} , 6.8 μV due to jitter and 7.25 μV due to the f_s . The overall uncertainty is 3.24 mV.

Table 4: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **frequency estimation (f)**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	2.5 nHz	$UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 2.3 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{\text{harm2}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 2.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 9 \cdot \text{jitter}_{\text{RMS}}(\text{s})$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot N$ N should be at least 20.000
Aftw	0.315 Hz	$UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 10^{-5e5 \cdot N}$ N should be at least 20.000 otherwise the equation above should be used $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
AMHFE	0.18 μHz	$UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 4.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot U_{\text{harm}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 1.8 \cdot \text{jitter}_{\text{RMS}}(\text{s})$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 30 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot N$
Resample	50 nHz	$UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 2.4 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot U_{\text{harm2}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 10^{-0.0005 \cdot N - 2}$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 3.6 \cdot \text{jitter}_{\text{RMS}}(\text{s})$ $UNC_f(\text{Hz}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-10} N$
Windowed	/	/

Table 5: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **fundamental voltage estimation (U_1)**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$3nV \cdot U_1(V)$	$UNC_{U_1}(V) = 1 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm5}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 6 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm4}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 2 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm3}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 4 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot U_{harm}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 0.03 \cdot U_{noise}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 325 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(s)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 5.5 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(Hz)$
Aftw	$0.25mV \cdot U_1(V)$	/
AMHFE	$0.17\mu V \cdot U_1(V)$	$UNC_{U_1}(V) = 7 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 3 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 400 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(s)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 5.2 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(Hz)$
Resample	$0.1mV \cdot U_1(V)$	$UNC_{U_1}(V) = 2.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm5}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 2.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm3}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm2}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 2.3 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot U_{noise}(V)$
Windowed	$0.25 mV \cdot U_1(V)$	$UNC_{U_1}(V) = 0.33 \cdot U_{harm5}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 0.33 \cdot U_{harm4}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 0.33 \cdot U_{harm3}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 0.33 \cdot U_{harm2}(V)$ $UNC_{U_1}(V) = 0.033 \cdot U_{harm}(V)$

Table 6: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for estimation of the **amplitude of the second voltage harmonic (U_{h2})**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$20 \text{ nV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot U_{harm5}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 6.4 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm4}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 9 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot U_{harm2}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 3.1 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 760 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 1.33 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$0.18 \text{ mV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 1.3 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{harm2}(\text{V})$
AMHFE	$0.2 \text{ } \mu\text{V} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 7.2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 680 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_2}(\text{V}) = 5.8 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$0.35 \text{ mV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	/
Windowed	/	/

Table 7: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **amplitude of the third voltage harmonic (U_{h3})**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$35 \text{ nV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 1.7 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot U_{harm5}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 6.4 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm4}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 5.4 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 2.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 3.1 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 720 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 8 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$0.7 \text{ mV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 6.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{harm3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 6.8 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$
AMHFE	$80 \text{ nV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 7.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 3 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 650 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{U_3}(\text{V}) = 6 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$0.3 \text{ mV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	/
Windowed	/	/

Table 8: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **amplitude of the fourth voltage harmonic (U_{h4})**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$0.15 \mu\text{V} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot U_{harm5}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 1.7 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot U_{harm4}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 3.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 3.1 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 7.9 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 6 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$1.8 \text{ mV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 1.75 \cdot 10^{-1} \cdot U_{harm4}(\text{V})$
AMHFE	$0.18 \mu\text{V} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 8.2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 3.1 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 900 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 6.5 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$80 \mu\text{V} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm5}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 3 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 1.3 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm2}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U_4}(\text{V}) = 0.25 \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$
Windowed	/	/

Table 9: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **amplitude of the fifth voltage harmonic (U_{h5})**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$60 \text{ nV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 4.2 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot U_{harm5}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 7 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm4}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{harm3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 1 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 3.1 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 8.1 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$ $f_s \geq 12.5 \text{ kHz}$
Aftw	$3.5 \text{ mV} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 0.34 \cdot U_{harm5}(\text{V})$
AMHFE	$0.18 \text{ } \mu\text{V} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 9 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 3.25 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 8.6 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 7 \cdot 10^{-10} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$90 \text{ } \mu\text{V} \cdot U_1(\text{V})$	$UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 4.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm4}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{harm3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{U5}(\text{V}) = 0.25 \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$
Windowed	/	/

Table 10: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **fundamental current estimation (I_1)**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$20 \text{ nA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 1.3 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 16 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 1 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 6 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 2.8 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$0.26 \text{ mA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	/
AMHFE	$0.16 \text{ }\mu\text{A} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 21 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 7.2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 2.7 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$80 \text{ }\mu\text{A} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 0.2 \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 2.1 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 2.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm2}(\text{A})$
Windowed	$0.26 \text{ mA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 0.33 \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 0.33 \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 0.33 \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 0.33 \cdot I_{harm2}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_1}(\text{A}) = 0.035 \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$

Table 11: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **amplitude of the second current harmonic (I_{h2})**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$80 \text{ nA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 2.4 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 3 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 4 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 6.4 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 9 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot I_{harm2}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 6.5 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$0.18 \text{ mA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 0.013 \cdot I_{harm2}(\text{A})$
AMHFE	$0.16 \text{ }\mu\text{A} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 3 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 35 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 7.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_2}(\text{A}) = 3 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$0.32 \text{ mA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	/
Windowed	/	/

Table 12: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **amplitude of the third current harmonic (I_{h3})**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$3.4 \text{ nA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 1.3 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 3.4 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 35 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 1.4 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 6 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 5.4 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 4 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 4 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$0.7 \text{ mA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 6.4 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$
AMHFE	$0.18 \text{ } \mu\text{A} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 3 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 33 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 7.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 3 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$0.11 \text{ mA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 0.19 \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 3.6 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I_{13}}(\text{A}) = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$
Windowed	/	/

Table 13: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **amplitude of the fourth current harmonic (I_{h4})**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$0.16 \mu\text{A} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 3.3 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 39 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 3.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 3 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$1.8 \text{ mA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 0.18 \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$
AMHFE	$0.16 \mu\text{A} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 0.03 \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 8 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 3.3 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$0.12 \text{ mA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 0.25 \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 4.8 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I4}(\text{A}) = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$
Windowed	/	/

Table 14: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **amplitude of the fifth current harmonic (I_{h5})**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$0.6 \mu\text{A} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 2.9 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 41 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$
Aftw	$4 \text{mA} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 0.34 \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$
AMHFE	$0.18 \mu\text{A} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 43 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 9 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 3.5 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$90 \mu\text{A} \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 0.23 \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 4.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{I5}(\text{A}) = 1.8 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$
Windowed	/	/

Table 15: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **phase estimation (φ)**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$36 \cdot 10^{-9}$ radians	$UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot U_{\text{harm}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 3 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 6.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot I_{\text{noise}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 6.1 \cdot \text{jitter}_{\text{RMS}}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 9 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot I_{\text{harm}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 9 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-9}$ radians	$UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 7.2 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{\text{noise}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 12.5 \cdot \text{jitter}_{\text{RMS}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 6.5 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
AMHFE	$0.8 \cdot 10^{-6}$ radians	$UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot U_{\text{harm}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 6.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{\text{noise}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 20 \cdot \text{jitter}_{\text{RMS}}(\text{s})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 4.3 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{\text{harm}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$0.35 \cdot 10^{-3}$ radians	/
Windowed	$65 \cdot 10^{-3}$ radians	$UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 9 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{\text{harm}5}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 9.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{\text{harm}4}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 9.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{\text{harm}3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 9.5 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{\text{harm}2}(\text{V})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 0.19 \cdot I_{\text{harm}5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 0.19 \cdot I_{\text{harm}4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 0.19 \cdot I_{\text{harm}3}(\text{A})$ $UNC_{\varphi}(\text{rad}) = 0.19 \cdot I_{\text{harm}2}(\text{A})$

Table 16: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **estimation of active power (P)**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$0.1 \mu\text{W} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1.6 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 0.16 \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 3 \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 3000 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 4.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 5.5 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$0.44 \text{ mW} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	/
AMHFE	$0.7 \mu\text{W} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{harm}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 0.31 \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 6 \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1 \cdot 10^4 \cdot jitter_{RMS}(\text{s})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 0.2 \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot I_{harm}(\text{A})$
Resample	$0.15 \text{ mW} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{harm5}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{harm3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1.3 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{harm2}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1 \cdot U_{noise}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 22 \cdot I_{noise}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 2.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$
Windowed	$0.42 \text{ mW} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_P(\text{W}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{harm5}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{harm4}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{harm3}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 5 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot U_{harm2}(\text{V})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1 \cdot I_{harm5}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1 \cdot I_{harm4}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1 \cdot I_{harm3}(\text{A})$ $UNC_P(\text{W}) = 1 \cdot I_{harm2}(\text{A})$

Table 17: Base accuracy and empirical equations (*i.e.*, relations between uncertainty and one systematically varied parameter) for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm defined for **estimation of apparent power (S)**.

Algorithm	Base accuracy	Dependencies
Aspline	$7 \text{ nVA} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 3.2 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot U_{\text{harm4}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 1 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot U_{\text{harm3}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot U_{\text{harm}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 0.15 \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 3.1 \cdot I_{\text{noise}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 3000 \cdot \text{jitter}_{\text{RMS}}(\text{s})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 6 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot I_{\text{harm4}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot I_{\text{harm3}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 3.8 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot I_{\text{harm}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 5.5 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Aftw	$0.45 \text{ mVA} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	/
AMHFE	$0.24 \text{ } \mu\text{VA} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 3.6 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{\text{harm}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 0.16 \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 3.1 \cdot I_{\text{noise}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 4000 \cdot \text{jitter}_{\text{RMS}}(\text{s})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 7.2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{\text{harm}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 4.8 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot f_s(\text{Hz})$
Resample	$0.14 \text{ mVA} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{\text{harm5}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 1 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{\text{harm3}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 1.2 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot U_{\text{harm2}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 0.9 \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 20 \cdot I_{\text{noise}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{\text{harm5}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{\text{harm4}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{\text{harm3}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 2 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot I_{\text{harm2}}(\text{A})$
Windowed	$0.42 \text{ mVA} \cdot U_1(\text{V}) \cdot I_1(\text{A})$	$UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 1.7 \cdot U_{\text{harm5}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 1.7 \cdot U_{\text{harm4}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 1.7 \cdot U_{\text{harm3}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 1.7 \cdot U_{\text{harm2}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 0.18 \cdot U_{\text{harm}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 0.22 \cdot U_{\text{noise}}(\text{V})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 4.5 \cdot I_{\text{noise}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 33 \cdot I_{\text{harm5}}(\text{A})$ $UNC_S(\text{VA}) = 33 \cdot I_{\text{harm4}}(\text{A})$

		$UNC_S(VA) = 33 \cdot I_{harm3}(A)$ $UNC_S(VA) = 33 \cdot I_{harm2}(A)$ $UNC_S(VA) = 3.4 \cdot I_{harm}(A)$
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3 Conclusion

In this document an uncertainty analysis for Aspline, Aftw, AMHFE, Resample and Windowed algorithm is presented. In the first chapter a Mante-Carlo based simulator written in Matlab environment is shown. The simulator contains three loop which gives sensitivity analysis for all output parameters (f , U_1 , U_{h2} , U_{h3} , U_{h4} , U_{h5} , I_1 , I_{h2} , I_{h3} , I_{h4} , I_{h5} , φ , P , and S) that are estimated by five algorithms when all 16 input parameters are systematically varied (N , f_s , $jitter_{RMS}$, U_{h2} , U_{h3} , U_{h4} , U_{h5} , U_h , U_{noise} , I_{h2} , I_{h3} , I_{h4} , I_{h5} , I_h , I_{noise} , N_{harm}). Additionally, each combination of systematically varied parameter has been repeated 50.000 times while varying 14 randomly varied input parameters to reliably define the uncertainty.

The Aspline and AMHFE generally show the lowest uncertainty for estimated parameters while the Aftw and Windowed generally show the highest uncertainty for all estimated parameters. On contrary, the Resample give low uncertainty for some estimated parameters while the others are estimated with much higher uncertainty.

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Appendix D DC decay time Algorithms and Monte Carlo analysis

DC decay parameters estimation

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1 Description of approaches

The algorithm should be able to estimate five parameters of sinewave function with DC decay transient according to Eq. 1 (U_{DC} , U_{AC} , B , f and φ). Especially important is time constant related to DC decay (B).

$$U(t) = U_{DC} \cdot e^{-Bt} + U_{AC} \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot f \cdot t + \varphi) \quad (1)$$

Three approaches have been developed and tested; the first one based on peak detection, the second one is based on fitting and the last one combines both approaches where the rough estimates are defined by *peak-detect* approach and these values are then used as initial guesses for fitting function.

1.1 *Peak-detect* approach

The principle of *peak-detect* approach is shown in Fig. 1 (Code A). First, the peaks are detected using the *peakseek* function (Code C), then the peaks are time shifted so the first peak appears at $t = 0$ s. The value time shift and the distances between the peaks correspond to initial phase and the period of the analysed signal, respectively. Peak detection and time shift reduces the number of parameters that needs to be estimated iteratively, Eq. 2. After estimating U_{DC}' , B and U_{AC} , the U_{DC} can be simply recalculated by knowing the estimated parameters U_{DC}' , B and initial time shift. This simplification not only significantly reduce the time for the calculation, but it makes the approach also very robust since the iterations does not stop when only a local minimum is found.

$$U(t') = U_{DC}' \cdot e^{-Bt'} + U_{AC} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1: Principle of *peak-detect* approach.

In order to test the algorithm, the reference signal was generated first using Eq. 3. The origin values of the parameters are:

- $A = 250$ V

- $B = 20$ /s
- $C = 230$ V
- $D = 50$ Hz
- $Noise = 0$

$$U(t) = A \cdot e^{-B \cdot t} + C \cdot \sin(2 \cdot \pi \cdot D \cdot t + E) + Noise \quad (3)$$

In the analysis only one parameter has been varied at the time while the other remained set to origin values. The only exception is initial phase of the sinewave (parameter E) which has been randomly varied between $\pm\pi$. For each variation of each parameter, 9.000 Monte-Carlo simulations have been made, and estimated parameters were tracked by *peak-detect* based algorithm. Additionally, the calculation time was measured for each simulation. The maximum, average and minimum errors for A , B , C , D , and $Noise$ variation and the calculation times for *peak-detect* approach are gathered in Tables 1-5.

Table 1: The variation of A parameter (U_{DC}) for *peak-detect* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: A (V)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
50	Max.	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.02	0.02
	Avr.	0.04	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00
	Min.	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00
100	Max.	0.10	0.07	0.00	0.04	0.01
	Avr.	0.08	0.04	0.00	0.03	0.00
	Min.	0.06	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00
150	Max.	0.14	0.10	0.00	0.06	0.01
	Avr.	0.12	0.07	0.00	0.04	0.00
	Min.	0.09	0.03	0.00	0.03	0.00
200	Max.	0.18	0.13	0.01	0.07	0.01
	Avr.	0.16	0.09	0.00	0.06	0.00
	Min.	0.13	0.06	0.00	0.05	0.00
250	Max.	0.22	0.16	0.01	0.09	0.01
	Avr.	0.20	0.12	0.01	0.07	0.00
	Min.	0.17	0.07	0.00	0.06	0.00
300	Max.	0.26	0.19	0.02	0.11	0.01
	Avr.	0.24	0.15	0.01	0.09	0.00
	Min.	0.20	0.10	0.00	0.07	0.00
350	Max.	0.35	0.26	0.03	0.14	0.01
	Avr.	0.31	0.20	0.02	0.12	0.00
	Min.	0.28	0.14	0.01	0.09	0.00

Table 2: The variation of B parameter (time decay) for *peak-detect* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: B (1/s)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
5	Max.	38.21	138.79	42.20	0.02	0.03
	Avr.	34.47	114.84	39.48	0.02	0.00
	Min.	30.68	114.74	37.55	0.01	0.00
10	Max.	8.29	27.11	10.74	0.05	0.01
	Avr.	6.56	18.16	8.08	0.04	0.00
	Min.	4.87	17.86	7.31	0.03	0.00
15	Max.	0.46	2.47	0.88	0.07	0.01
	Avr.	0.23	0.36	0.17	0.06	0.00
	Min.	0.15	0.29	0.12	0.05	0.00
20	Max.	0.22	0.16	0.01	0.09	0.01
	Avr.	0.20	0.12	0.01	0.07	0.00
	Min.	0.17	0.07	0.00	0.06	0.00

Table 3: The variation of C parameter (U_{AC}) for *peak-detect* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: C (V)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
100	Max.	0.49	0.38	0.07	0.21	0.03
	Avr.	0.45	0.29	0.04	0.17	0.00
	Min.	0.40	0.22	0.02	0.14	0.00
200	Max.	0.25	0.19	0.02	0.10	0.01
	Avr.	0.23	0.14	0.01	0.08	0.00
	Min.	0.20	0.10	0.00	0.07	0.00
230	Max.	0.22	0.16	0.01	0.09	0.01
	Avr.	0.20	0.12	0.01	0.07	0.00
	Min.	0.17	0.07	0.00	0.06	0.00
300	Max.	0.17	0.13	0.01	0.07	0.01
	Avr.	0.15	0.09	0.00	0.06	0.00
	Min.	0.12	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.00
400	Max.	0.13	0.10	0.00	0.05	0.01
	Avr.	0.11	0.06	0.00	0.04	0.00
	Min.	0.09	0.03	0.00	0.03	0.00

Table 4: The variation of D parameter (f) for *peak-detect* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: D (Hz)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
45	Max.	0.27	0.21	0.02	0.11	0.04
	Avr.	0.24	0.15	0.01	0.09	0.00
	Min.	0.20	0.10	0.00	0.06	0.00
50	Max.	0.22	0.16	0.01	0.09	0.07
	Avr.	0.20	0.12	0.01	0.07	0.00
	Min.	0.17	0.07	0.00	0.06	0.00
55	Max.	0.19	0.13	0.01	0.08	0.01
	Avr.	0.16	0.10	0.00	0.06	0.00
	Min.	0.14	0.07	0.00	0.05	0.00
60	Max.	0.16	0.12	0.01	0.07	0.01
	Avr.	0.14	0.08	0.00	0.05	0.00
	Min.	0.12	0.05	0.00	0.04	0.00
65	Max.	0.14	0.10	0.01	0.06	0.00
	Avr.	0.12	0.07	0.00	0.05	0.00
	Min.	0.10	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.00

Table 5: The variation of *RMS noise* parameter for *peak-detect* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: Noise (V_{rms})		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
0	Max	0.24	0.19	0.02	0.10	0.06
	Avr.	0.20	0.12	0.01	0.07	0.00
	Min.	0.15	0.05	0.00	0.05	0.00
0.1	Max	5.89	8.66	3.98	0.74	0.01
	Avr.	0.26	0.29	0.10	0.08	0.00
	Min.	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
1	Max	99.93	97.01	103.87	2.89	0.01
	Avr.	14.83	12.69	8.80	0.38	0.00
	Min.	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

The *peak-detect* approach is quite fast and robust, but it requires at least three peaks for accurate estimation. The maximal errors for the approach are quite small. However, the minimal error is almost always non-zero, so this approach is not capable to provide “*exact*” results.

1.2 Fitting approach

For the *fitting* approach we used the function which is already implemented in Matlab (Curve Fitting Toolbox). The user must specify the fitting function and roughly give the initial guesses. The functions that were used in the analysis are given below:

```
function=fittype('A*exp(-B*t)+C*sin(2*pi*D*t+E)', 'indep', 't');
result=fit(t_sample,x_sample, function, 'start', [110, 0.03, 200, 51, 0.1]);
```

The testing of the approach was performed using the same method as for the *peak-detect* approach. The results are shown in Tables 6-10.

Table 6: The variation of A parameter (U_{DC}) for *fit* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: A (V)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
50	Max.	71.96	92.79	121.40	315.04	2.28
	Avr.	1.01	3.40	2.92	0.17	0.26
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.17
100	Max.	49.31	75.06	121.38	298.56	1.89
	Avr.	1.23	3.10	3.33	0.13	0.25
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.16
150	Max.	39.65	66.55	113.34	265.05	2.22
	Avr.	1.59	2.92	3.75	0.14	0.25
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.14
200	Max.	39.76	60.43	112.48	275.18	1.94
	Avr.	1.63	2.50	3.68	0.17	0.25
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.14
250	Max.	42.22	57.90	112.47	315.03	2.19
	Avr.	1.63	2.22	3.44	0.27	0.25
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
300	Max.	46.45	57.26	110.68	305.13	2.18
	Avr.	1.51	1.87	3.02	0.16	0.24
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.16
350	Max.	53.39	83.32	108.80	525.02	2.08
	Avr.	0.66	0.71	1.44	0.25	0.22
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.16

Table 7: The variation of B parameter (time decay) for *fit* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: B (1/s)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
5	Max.	30.97	64.84	121.58	225.08	2.26
	Avr.	0.69	1.46	2.55	0.14	0.23
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
10	Max.	34.32	46.77	121.45	265.07	2.09
	Avr.	1.06	1.45	3.17	0.10	0.24
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.14
15	Max.	38.21	50.74	112.53	315.11	1.90
	Avr.	1.15	1.54	2.91	0.22	0.23
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.14
20	Max.	42.22	57.90	107.19	335.12	2.15
	Avr.	1.77	2.41	3.70	0.18	0.25
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.16

Table 8: The variation of C parameter (U_{AC}) for *fit* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: C (V)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
100	Max.	88.75	55.58	238.87	245.13	2.41
	Avr.	1.16	1.28	10.96	1.65	0.31
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
200	Max.	42.91	57.22	112.48	265.15	2.09
	Avr.	1.95	2.59	4.35	0.18	0.27
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
230	Max.	42.22	57.90	112.47	245.15	2.02
	Avr.	1.70	2.32	3.63	0.14	0.25
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
300	Max.	44.38	64.41	99.01	325.06	1.97
	Avr.	1.00	1.38	2.17	0.14	0.22
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
400	Max.	54.09	85.02	106.64	185.12	7004.35
	Avr.	6.34	10.02	6.90	0.09	1.35
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.17

Table 9: The variation of D parameter (f) for fit approach analysis.

Varied parameter: D (Hz)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
45	Max.	176.48	113.29	623.59	439.76	1097.17
	Avr.	18.60	21.37	78.44	22.17	0.92
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.16
50	Max.	42.22	57.90	108.82	295.13	2.34
	Avr.	1.72	2.36	3.59	0.24	0.25
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
55	Max.	27.59	86.45	200.00	486.29	2.20
	Avr.	6.28	7.50	32.17	8.56	0.54
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
60	Max.	35.33	99.53	185.62	346.05	2.22
	Avr.	11.93	13.16	84.56	24.45	0.71
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.14
65	Max.	23.88	165.61	287.47	296.24	2.19
	Avr.	11.69	13.10	89.58	26.43	0.82
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.14

Table 10: The variation of RMS noise parameter for fit approach analysis.

Varied parameter: Noise (V_{rms})		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	calc. time (s)
0	Max.	42.22	57.90	108.82	295.13	2.40
	Avr.	1.72	2.35	3.61	0.19	0.25
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
0.1	Max.	42.22	57.90	112.47	265.13	2.26
	Avr.	1.70	2.32	3.61	0.14	0.25
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.15
1	Max.	42.23	57.90	108.83	275.17	2.05
	Avr.	1.65	2.26	3.48	0.17	0.24
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0.14

The results showed that the calculation time is significantly longer compared to *peak-detect* approach. Additionally, the maximal and average errors are for all four estimated parameters significantly higher than the errors observed for the *peak-detect* approach. However, the minimal errors are typically 0 which indicates that the “accurate” estimation is possible with *fitting* approach. The reason for that behaviour is most probably in initial guesses which remained the same for all simulation and for all varied parameters. Sometimes the fit function quickly finds just the local minimum and the errors are then quite significant. On contrary, if the global minimum is found that the “accurate” estimation is also possible.

1.3 Combined approach

To further improve the estimation of the DC decay parameters we combined both approaches. In the first step the parameters are estimated by the *peak-detect* approach and then these values are used as initial guesses in the *fit* function. Matlab code for *combined* approach is shown in Code B.

The combined approach has been tested using the same method as for *peak-detect* and *fit* approach. The results are shown in Tables 11-15.

Table 11: The variation of A parameter (U_{DC}) for *combined* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: A (V)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)
50	Max.	0	0	0	0
100	Max.	0	0	0	0
150	Max.	0	0	0	0
200	Max.	0	0	0	0
250	Max.	0	0	0	0
300	Max.	0	0	0	0
350	Max.	0	0	0	0
400	Max.	0	0	0	0

Table 12: The variation of B parameter (time constant) for *combined* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: B (1/s)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)
5	Max.	0	0	0	0
10	Max.	0	0	0	0
15	Max.	0	0	0	0
20	Max.	0	0	0	0

Table 13: The variation of C parameter (U_{AC}) for *combined* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: C (V)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)
100	Max.	0	0	0	0
200	Max.	0	0	0	0
230	Max.	0	0	0	0
300	Max.	0	0	0	0
400	Max.	0	0	0	0

Table 14: The variation of D parameter (f) for *combined* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: D (Hz)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)
45	Max.	0	0	0	0
50	Max.	0	0	0	0
55	Max.	0	0	0	0
60	Max.	0	0	0	0
65	Max.	0	0	0	0

Table 15: The variation of *RMS noise* parameter for *combined* approach analysis.

Varied parameter: Noise (V _{rms})		<i>A</i> _{error} (%)	<i>B</i> _{error} (%)	<i>C</i> _{error} (%)	<i>D</i> _{error} (%)
0	Max.	0	0	0	0
	Avr.	0	0	0	0
	Min.	0	0	0	0
0.001	Max.	4.4e-5	6.5e-5	1.7e-5	0
	Avr.	9.3e-6	1.3e-5	3.4e-6	0
	Min.	0	0	0	0
0.1	Max.	4.6e-3	7.3e-3	1.7e-3	1.1e-4
	Avr.	9.3e-4	1.3e-3	3.6e-4	1.9e-5
	Min.	0	0	0	0
1	Max.	83.7	95.8	123	75.4
	Avr.	4.1	1.4	5.0	0.2
	Min.	0	1e-5	0	0

All errors are 0 and the calculation time was roughly double compared to the time needed for the calculation with only *peak-detect* approach (not shown here). However, all analysis so far were dealing with non-disturbed signals (Tables 1-4, 5-9 and 11-14). When the noisy signal is analysed by *combined* approach, we also observed non-zero errors which increases with increasing noise levels. Nevertheless, the results of *combined* approach are very promising even for very high levels of noise (*i.e.*, $U_{noise} = 0.1$ V) and become useless only for extreme cases when 1 V noise is added to 230 V AC signal with 250 V DC decay signal.

To further analyse the *combined* approach, we repeated the systematic variation of *A*, *B*, *C* and *D* parameters but in this case the 0.1 V RMS noise was always added to the signal. In this analysis the phase has been also randomly varied between $\pm\pi$ in each Monte-Carlo analysis as before, but in this case the phase error has been also analysed (E_{error}). The results are shown in Tables 16-19. The errors are generally significantly below 0.01%. The only major exception is $U_{AC} = 100$ V (Table 18) where a quite high errors have been observed in a few numbers of simulations. But generally, also in this combination of input parameters a reliable estimation could be obtained.

Table 16: The variation of *A* parameter (U_{DC}) for *combined* approach analysis with 0.1 V RMS noise.

Varied parameter: <i>A</i> (V)		<i>A</i> _{error} (%)	<i>B</i> _{error} (%)	<i>C</i> _{error} (%)	<i>D</i> _{error} (%)	<i>E</i> _{error} (%)
50	Max.	0.022	0.032	0.002	0	0.001
100	Max.	0.011	0.017	0.002	0	0.001
150	Max.	0.007	0.010	0.002	0	0.001
200	Max.	0.006	0.008	0.002	0	0.001
250	Max.	0.005	0.006	0.002	0	0.001
300	Max.	0.004	0.006	0.002	0	0.001
350	Max.	0.003	0.005	0.002	0	0.001
400	Max.	0.003	0.004	0.002	0	0.001

Table 17: The variation of B parameter (time constant) for *combined* approach analysis with 0.1 V RMS noise.

Varied parameter: B (1/s)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	E_{error} (%)
5	Max.	0.003	0.006	0.002	0	0.001
10	Max.	0.004	0.006	0.002	0	0.001
15	Max.	0.004	0.006	0.002	0	0.001
20	Max.	0.005	0.007	0.002	0	0.001

Table 18: The variation of C parameter (U_{AC}) for *combined* approach analysis with 0.1 V RMS noise.

Varied parameter: C (V)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	E_{error} (%)
100	Max.	24.314	6.677	65.402	0.145	1.205
	Avr.	0.060	0.009	0.188	0	0.003
	Min.	0	0	0	0	0
200	Max.	0.005	0.008	0.002	0	0.001
230	Max.	0.004	0.007	0.002	0	0.001
300	Max.	0.004	0.006	0.002	0	0
400	Max.	0.004	0.006	0.001	0	0

Table 19: The variation of D parameter (f) for *combined* approach analysis with 0.1 V RMS noise.

Varied parameter: D (Hz)		A_{error} (%)	B_{error} (%)	C_{error} (%)	D_{error} (%)	E_{error} (%)
45	Max.	0.005	0.006	0.002	0	0.001
50	Max.	0.005	0.007	0.002	0	0.001
55	Max.	0.004	0.006	0.002	0	0.001
60	Max.	0.004	0.007	0.002	0	0.001
65	Max.	0.004	0.006	0.002	0	0.001

Code A: Matlab code for *DecayEstimation_Peaks*

```
function [A0_recalculated, B0, C0, D0] = DecayEstimation_Peaks(t_sample,x_sample,
Fs, PlotEnable, delta, N_for, N_max, N_loop_Max)
%DecayEstimation_Peaks estimated parameters from AC sinewave function with
%DC decay.
% INPUT VARIABLES:
% t_sample           time vector
% x_sample           sampled signal
% Fs                 sampling frequency (could be calculated from t_sample)
% PlotEnable         plot the waveforms before and after estimation
% delta              criteria which terminates the loop
% N_for              maximal number of loops, each time delta is 10 times
lower
% N_max              number of iteration for both variables
% N_loop_Max         number of iteration for one variable
% OUTPUT VARIABLES:
% A0                 DC voltage at the first sample
% B0                 exponential decay of the DC voltage
% C0                 AC voltage (maximal value)
% D0                 frequency

% INITIAL GUESS
Fs=1/(t_sample(2)-t_sample(1));
minpeakdist=0.9*(Fs/60);
[locs A_pks]=peakseek(x_sample, minpeakdist);

t_peaks0=t_sample(locs);
premik=t_peaks0(1);
t_peaks=t_peaks0-t_peaks0(1);           %time shift of the signal
D0=1/mean(diff(t_peaks(2:end)));        %frequency estimation
C0=A_pks(end);
A0=A_pks(1)-C0;
B0=52;
x_meas=A_pks';
t=t_peaks;

% PLOT
if PlotEnable==1
    figure(1)
    plot(t_sample, x_sample, 'b', t_peaks0, A_pks, '*')
    figure (2)
    plot(t, x_meas, '*')
end

% CALCULATION
delta=delta*10;
konec=0;
for i=1:N_for
    delta=delta/10; %v odstotkih
    N=0;
    konec=0;
    while N < N_max && konec < 2
        %%A: DC vrednost
        N_loop=0;
        konec_ena=0;
        while N_loop<N_loop_Max && konec_ena==0
            A1=A0*(100-delta)/100;
            A2=A0;
            A3=A0*(100+delta)/100;

            cost1=sum((x_meas-(A1*exp(-B0*t)+x_meas(1)-A1)).^2);
            cost2=sum((x_meas-(A2*exp(-B0*t)+x_meas(1)-A2)).^2);
            cost3=sum((x_meas-(A3*exp(-B0*t)+x_meas(1)-A3)).^2);
            cost= [cost1, cost2 , cost3];
            [minimum,lokacija]=min(cost);
            if lokacija == 2
```

```

        konec=1;
        konec_ena=1;
    elseif lokacija==1
        konec=0;
        A0=A1;
    else
        konec=0;
        A0=A3;
    end
    N_loop=N_loop+1;
end

%B: DC tau
N_loop=0;
konec_ena=0;
while N_loop<N_loop_Max && konec_ena==0
    B1=B0*(100-delta)/100;
    B2=B0;
    B3=B0*(100+delta)/100;
    cost1=sum((x_meas-(A0*exp(-B1*t)+x_meas(1)-A0)).^2);
    cost2=sum((x_meas-(A0*exp(-B2*t)+x_meas(1)-A0)).^2);
    cost3=sum((x_meas-(A0*exp(-B3*t)+x_meas(1)-A0)).^2);
    cost= [cost1, cost2, cost3];
    [minimum,lokacija]=min(cost);
    if lokacija == 2
        konec=konec+1;
        konec_ena=1;
    elseif lokacija==1
        konec=0;
        B0=B1;
    else
        konec=0;
        B0=B3;
    end
    N_loop=N_loop+1;
end
N=N+1;
end
N;
end%zanka for
A0_recalculated=A0*exp(B0*premik);
C0=A_pks(1)-A0;
end %function

```

Code B: Matlab code for *Combined* approach

```
function [A_est, B_est, C_est, D_est, E_est] =
DecayEstimation_Peaks(t_sample,x_sample, PlotEnable, delta, N_for, N_max,
N_loop_Max)
%DecayEstimation_Peaks estimated parameters from AC sinewave function with
%DC decay.
% INPUT VARIABLES:
% t_sample      time vector
% x_sample      sampled signal
% PlotEnable    plot the waveforms before and after estimation
% delta         criteria which terminates the loop
% N_for         maximal number of loops, each time delta is 10 times lower
% N_max         number of iteration ofr both variables
% N_loop_Max    number of iteration for one variable
% OUTPUT VARIABLES:
% A_est         estimated DC valtage at the first sample
% B_est         estimated exponential decay of the DC voltage
% C_est         estimated AC voltage (maximal value)
% D_est         estimated frequency
% E_est         estimated phase

% INITIAL GUESSES
Fs=1/(t_sample(2)-t_sample(1));
minpeakdist=0.9*(Fs/60);
[locs, A_pks]=peakseek(x_sample, minpeakdist);

t_peaks0=t_sample(locs);
premik=t_peaks0(1);
t_peaks=t_peaks0-t_peaks0(1);           %time shift of the signal
D0=1/mean(diff(t_peaks(2:end)));       %frequency estimation
C0=A_pks(end);
A0=A_pks(1)-C0;
B0=52;
x_meas=A_pks';
t=t_peaks;

% PLOT
if PlotEnable==1
    figure(1)
    plot(t_sample, x_sample, 'b', t_peaks0, A_pks, '*')
    figure (2)
    plot(t, x_meas, '*')
end

% PEAK DETECT
delta=delta*10;
konec=0;
for i=1:N_for
    delta=delta/10; %v odstotkih
    N=0;
    konec=0;
    while N < N_max && konec < 2
        %%A: DC vrednost
        N_loop=0;
        konec_ena=0;
        while N_loop<N_loop_Max && konec_ena==0
            A1=A0*(100-delta)/100;
            A2=A0;
            A3=A0*(100+delta)/100;

            cost1=sum((x_meas-(A1*exp(-B0*t)+x_meas(1)-A1)).^2);
            cost2=sum((x_meas-(A2*exp(-B0*t)+x_meas(1)-A2)).^2);
            cost3=sum((x_meas-(A3*exp(-B0*t)+x_meas(1)-A3)).^2);
            cost= [cost1, cost2, cost3];
            [minimum,lokacija]=min(cost);
            if lokacija == 2
```

```

        konec=1;
        konec_ena=1;
    elseif lokacija==1
        konec=0;
        A0=A1;
    else
        konec=0;
        A0=A3;
    end
    N_loop=N_loop+1;
end

%B
N_loop=0;
konec_ena=0;
while N_loop<N_loop_Max && konec_ena==0
    B1=B0*(100-delta)/100;
    B2=B0;
    B3=B0*(100+delta)/100;
    cost1=sum((x_meas-(A0*exp(-B1*t)+x_meas(1)-A0)).^2);
    cost2=sum((x_meas-(A0*exp(-B2*t)+x_meas(1)-A0)).^2);
    cost3=sum((x_meas-(A0*exp(-B3*t)+x_meas(1)-A0)).^2);
    cost= [cost1, cost2, cost3];
    [minimum,lokacija]=min(cost);
    if lokacija == 2
        konec=konec+1;
        konec_ena=1;
    elseif lokacija==1
        konec=0;
        B0=B1;
    else
        konec=0;
        B0=B3;
    end
    N_loop=N_loop+1;
end
N=N+1;
end
N;
end
A0_recalculated=A0*exp(B0*premik);
C0=A_pks(1)-A0;
E0=-premik*D0*2*pi+pi/2;
if E0>pi
    E0=E0-2*pi;
end
if E0<-pi
    E0=E0+2*pi;
end

%FIT
funkcija=fitttype('A*exp(-B*t)+C*sin(2*pi*D*t+E)', 'indep', 't');
rezultat=fit(t_sample,x_sample, funkcija, 'start', [A0_recalculated, B0, C0,
D0, E0]);
A_est=rezultat.A;
B_est=rezultat.B;
C_est=rezultat.C;
D_est=rezultat.D;
E_est=rezultat.E;
end

```

Code C: Matlab code for *Peakseek* function

```
function [locs pks]=peakseek(x,minpeakdist,minpeakh)
% Alternative to the findpeaks function. This thing runs much much faster.
% It really leaves findpeaks in the dust. It also can handle ties between
% peaks. Findpeaks just erases both in a tie. Shame on findpeaks.
%
% x is a vector input (generally a timecourse)
% minpeakdist is the minimum desired distance between peaks (optional, defaults to
1)
% minpeakh is the minimum height of a peak (optional)
%
% (c) 2010
% Peter O'Connor
% peter<dot>ed<dot>oconnor .AT. gmail<dot>com
if size(x,2)==1, x=x'; end
% Find all maxima and ties
locs=find(x(2:end-1)>=x(1:end-2) & x(2:end-1)>=x(3:end))+1;
if nargin<2, minpeakdist=1; end % If no minpeakdist specified, default to 1.
if nargin>2 % If there's a minpeakheight
    locs(x(locs)<=minpeakh)=[];
end
if minpeakdist>1
    while 1
        del=diff(locs)<minpeakdist;
        if ~any(del), break; end
        pks=x(locs);
        [garb mins]=min([pks(del) ; pks([false del])]); %#ok<ASGLU>
        deln=find(del);
        deln=[deln(mins==1) deln(mins==2)+1];
        locs(deln)=[];
    end
end
if nargin>1,
    pks=x(locs);
end
end
```